

Chapter 2 How does business depend on biodiversity? ¹

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Executive summary

1. All business sectors depend on biodiversity and associated nature's contribution to people (*established but incomplete*) {2.2}. Businesses depend on aspects of biodiversity or nature's contributions to people for their business operations. This dependency is at their operational level and through reliance on biodiversity throughout the value chain {2.2.1}. Businesses not only depend on material nature's contributions to people, but also on regulating and non-material benefits {2.2.1, 2.5.4}. Dependencies on biodiversity span over distances and time {2.2.3}. Limited understanding of dependencies can undermine long-term, sustainable business practices.

2. The magnitude and risk of dependencies vary highly across businesses with some businesses and economies having larger dependencies than others (*established but incomplete*) {2.2.2, 2.5.3}. Economies of countries depend considerably on biodiversity: for some countries, their gross domestic product depends between 36 per cent and 98 per cent moderately or highly on ecosystems {2.4.3}. Examples show that the individual nature's contributions to people can make up 8 per cent of a country's GDP and contribute billions to national economies, such as pest control services at \$70 million, pollination services for agriculture at \$12-34 billion, and habitat provision that supports species of interest to tourism at \$22-39 billion {2.5.2}. The associated physical risk depends on the magnitude of the dependency, substitutability of nature-related dependencies, competition over resources, and the long-term availability, accessibility and stability of a sustainable supply of the nature's contribution to people, which all vary across space {2.2.2}. Dependencies become impacts on biodiversity if their magnitude is larger than sustainable use levels {2.2.1}, and these impacts can negatively affect other stakeholders as well as the business itself {2.8} (**Chapter 3**). Dependencies vary across sectors, and within sub-sectors, across different natural conditions and geographies (*well established*) {2.5}.

3. The physical, transition and systemic risks associated with business dependencies on biodiversity and nature's contribution to people are acknowledged but rarely assessed and quantified, despite the risk to nature, businesses and society (*established but incomplete*) {2.2.4, 2.5.5}. Physical dependency risks are highly specific to individual businesses and their context, but methods are lacking to reliably quantify differences in nature-related dependencies between businesses, sectors, production methods and regions {2.4.3, 2.5.5}. Entities in the enabling business environment, including the financial sector, share business' nature-related dependencies {2.5.3}. Transition risk assessments related to the market, economic, technological or regulatory changes in transitions towards sustainability are emerging in the financial sector but otherwise rare {2.5.3}. Risk assessments that use systems-thinking to quantitatively assess systemic future risks to business dependencies on biodiversity or nature's contributions to people remain limited and constitute a knowledge gap.

4. To date, the knowledge base on business dependencies is largely focused on a few sectors (*well established*) {2.5}. The scientific knowledge base on the dependency of businesses on biodiversity and nature's contributions to people has focused on a few sectors {2.5}. Sectors which have been studied most, especially at subnational scale, include the agriculture, forestry and fishing, arts, entertainment and recreation, and water supply and waste management sectors {2.5.4}. The majority of sectors have not been studied.

5. There are considerable differences in the amount of academic evidence for dependencies on different types of nature's contributions to people (*established but incomplete*) {2.5}. Studies in the agricultural sector mostly focus on the role of pollinators in crop production {2.5.2, 2.5.4}. All sectors use water supply, purification or flow regulation for production or in their value chain. Some sectors depend more on non-material nature's contributions to people, while others rely more on

regulating nature's contribution to people, for instance, flood or pest control {2.4.1, 2.4.3}. More evidence is available for Europe, the Americas and Asia than for Africa and Oceania (*established but incomplete*) {2.8}.

6. A variety of methods has been used to document the dependencies of business on nature's contribution to people (*well established*) {2.3, 2.4}. Methods include environmental-economic models, biophysical and ecological approaches, participatory monitoring and mapping approaches monetary valuation methods, socio-cultural valuation methods {2.3}, as well as scenario analysis integrated & synthesizing methods, and socio-cultural valuation methods, {2.4}. Biophysical and ecological approaches and monetary valuation methods are used often {2.3.2}. There is less evidence for dependencies based on socio-cultural valuations {2.3}. Most dependency studies use quantitative methods, metrics and indicators to assess a diverse set of values, but this may risk overlooking values that are more accurately expressed in qualitative terms including some socio-cultural and community values {2.3.5}.

7. Different methods express dependencies in different metrics, but there is no standardised set of metrics for business dependencies on biodiversity or nature's contributions to people (*established but incomplete*) {2.5}. Quantitative measurements of dependencies of businesses on nature's contributions to people are not consistent, and units of measurements also vary {2.4.3}. Biophysical and ecological approaches mainly capture dependencies in terms of metrics such as increased yields in production, tons of crops or timber harvested, and volumes of water consumed, or quality of products {2.4.3, 2.5.4}. Economic models and monetary valuation methods assess economic value and risk to businesses in monetary units {2.4.3, 2.5.4}. Emerging regulatory pressure such as the European Union's Corporate Sustainability Reporting Directive is pushing towards more standardisation in metrics and reporting standards {2.4.3}.

8. Most methods to assess business dependencies on biodiversity and nature's contributions to people are focused on examining direct dependencies, with fewer methods suited for assessing upstream value chain dependencies (*established but incomplete*) {2.3, 2.4}. Methods such as biophysical and ecological assessments and monetary valuation are well-established for capturing direct dependencies; and provide context-specific data if applied at local scales {2.3.2, 2.3.4}. However, value chain dependencies, such as raw material transport or intermediary nature's contributions to people supporting production, are less frequently captured. For trade dependencies, large-scale environment-extended economic models are required, but these methods rarely use context-specific data, making them suitable for screening and ex-ante evaluation but less so for monitoring and evaluation {2.3.1}. Combining multiple approaches to measure value chain dependencies is necessary to assess the full scope of business reliance on biodiversity and thus the associated risks and opportunities for resilience within supply chains {2.4.1} but require more spatially and temporally detailed approaches {2.2.3}. Factors contributing to this include data gaps on the location and magnitude of business activities and a lack of traceability of material flows and impacts through value chains.

9. Uptake of available methods that can provide information on business dependency on nature's contribution to people is lacking (*well established*) {2.5}. Business dependence on ecosystem services is significant but understudied. Two recent reviews of the practices of large global businesses find that less than 1 per cent have assessed their dependencies {2.5.5}. Growing uptake is providing evidence of the potential of dependency assessment for identifying business opportunities and mitigating nature-related risks {2.6.2}, and for governments to monitor compliance with sustainability regulations {2.6.1}. Important barriers for uptake of nature-related risk management include access to reliable data and reliable models and scenarios {2.5.5}. Various integrated decision-support methods can help assessments of different values and dependencies {2.4.1}, but guidance on

assessing dependencies at every step of the value chain and attributing these to individual businesses is lacking.

10. Conventional businesses can be dependent on Indigenous and local knowledge and can learn from the ways in which Indigenous Peoples and local communities' businesses support and protect biodiversity (*established but incomplete*) {2.7}. Indigenous Peoples and local communities have relationships with nature and are among the most directly dependent stakeholder group on nature, as their ways of life and livelihoods are often closely connected to nature for food, medicine and cultural and economic activities {2.7.1}. Indigenous Peoples and local communities often have cultural values that recognise the mutual interrelationships between nature and people {2.7.1}. Indigenous and local knowledge, including insights related to medicine and art, is not only critical to assess dependencies, but also a valuable source of innovation and product development that has both inspired and been used by businesses {2.7.2}. Indigenous business models provide examples of business activities within environmental and social sustainability boundaries, but this type of knowledge has been disregarded and neglected {2.7.2}.

11. Nature-related dependencies of businesses arise from their interactions with Indigenous Peoples and local communities and other businesses. This interconnection yields significant positive and negative consequences in terms of risks and opportunities (*established but incomplete*) {2.7}. Business activities can either improve or harm biodiversity and nature's contribution to people upon which they and other businesses and local communities depend {2.7.2}. Business dependencies on nature can conflict with Indigenous Peoples and local communities' rights and restrict their access to land. For example, demand for minerals vital to the clean energy transition has escalated these risks, with mining projects frequently overlapping Indigenous territories: 80 per cent of lithium projects are located on Indigenous lands, and water scarcity in these regions compounds the risks of pollution {2.7.2}. Overexploitation of ecosystems can have adverse effects on commercial activities and on Indigenous Peoples and local communities.

12. Businesses must navigate complex trade-offs between profitability and broader societal needs in the context of their dependencies on nature's contributions to people, while realising synergies provides opportunities that are rarely seized (*established but incomplete*) {2.8}. Shared dependencies and objectives of businesses and other societal actors on biodiversity give rise to trade-offs and synergies (2.8). Trade-offs, evidenced in multiple studies, affect not only business profitability but also conservation and sustainable use of biodiversity, Indigenous Peoples and local communities, and other social and environmental priorities. Synergies present opportunities for partnerships and collaborations to secure value chains, mitigate risks, reduce conflicts, enhance equitable benefit sharing, and enhance business operations, but their realisation is less well evidenced {2.8}. Such synergies require innovative approaches that account for diverse values, worldviews and power dynamics to ensure that sustainability efforts create positive outcomes across different sectors and communities {2.5}. Different methods are available to support civil society and public and private sector entities design incentive schemes to promote and award sustainable behaviour {2.6}. Integrating these considerations into corporate decision-making can help businesses transition from merely mitigating negative impacts to actively contributing to environmental and social well-being through managing their dependencies sustainably {2.6.2, 2.8}.

13. Knowledge gaps remain for context-specific dependencies for several regions and sectors, but do not prevent short-term action towards dependency assessment and risk mitigation (*well established*) {2.9} Existing tools allow measuring certain nature's contributions to people in certain locations, but large knowledge gaps and data constraints remain in quantifying spatial and temporally explicit dependencies using scientifically-robust data {2.2.3}. Biophysical and ecological approaches are mostly used but often lack sufficient context-specific data – especially in remote areas, for understudied species and for dependencies along the value chain – limiting accurate nature dependency

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measurement and predictive models {2.3.2}. Standardized business-relevant indicators and metrics for assessing nature-related dependencies and risks are absent {2.4.3}. The use of scenario analysis and long-term outlooks is rare and limited to short-term shock assessments rather than longer-term dynamics {2.4.2, 2.5.5}. Due to these gaps, the lack of long-term, longitudinal studies limits understanding of sustainable business reliance on biodiversity and nature's contributions to people.

2.1. Introduction

All businesses are dependent on biodiversity for sustainability, resilience and financial performance (Dasgupta, 2021; zu Ermgassen et al., 2022). The dependence of human well-being and economic activity on biodiversity was highlighted in the late 1990s (Costanza et al., 1997; Daily, 1997) and widely publicized in the Millennium Ecosystem Assessment (2005) and the Global assessment report of the Intergovernmental Science-Policy Platform on Biodiversity and Ecosystem Services (IPBES, 2019a). Costanza et al. (2021) estimated that only ~22 per cent of the global ecosystem value is reflected in global Gross Domestic Product (GDP), yet provisioning ecosystem services², such as food, raw materials, and recreation, alone account for 36 per cent of global GDP. PricewaterhouseCoopers (PwC) reports that over half (55 per cent) of global GDP – about \$58 trillion – is generated in economic sectors moderately or highly dependent on biodiversity (Evison et al., 2023; White et al., 2020). This dependency extends beyond just species to their genetic resources such as digital sequence information (DSI) used by many sector for economic reasons (Brink & Van Hintum, 2022; ICF et al., 2020). Ecosystem degradation poses economic risks for businesses. As countries across the globe adopt natural capital accounting, they recognise the dependence of their economies and businesses on biodiversity. Similarly, leading businesses across diverse industries are recognizing the importance of integrating natural capital into their strategy and operations, and the financial sector is assessing natural-capital related risks and opportunities in relation to its investments (White et al., 2020). For example, the Dutch asset manager ACTIAM evaluates natural capital impacts and dependencies of businesses it invests in, believing these influence financial performance (White et al., 2020). Local communities are also increasingly recognising natural capital as an investment opportunity to increase community resilience (Musavengane & Kloppers, 2020).

Businesses and sectors depend on biodiversity in different ways. Biodiversity serves as a direct input in production. Businesses use raw materials to produce goods and services that are sold to consumers or other businesses. Examples include the use of wood in construction, water in manufacturing, or plants or microbes in pharmaceuticals. When substitutes exist, dependency risk is lower, but some businesses rely entirely on natural raw materials. Biodiversity enables production processes, as seen in crop production's dependence on bee pollinators. Pollinator-dependent crops account for 30-35 per cent of the global crop production (Klein et al., 2007). Dependencies extend through value chains. Therefore, business dependence on biodiversity poses physical business risks when biodiversity is degraded. The exposure to biodiversity dependency risks of Bloomberg World Index listed companies in terms of total enterprise value is estimated to be four times larger than their exposure to biodiversity impact risk (Carvalho et al., 2023a). For example, in 2018 about 21 per cent of the largest global listed businesses and \$20 trillion (17 per cent) in total enterprise value were exposed to material biodiversity dependency risk (Carvalho et al., 2023a).

Many business dependencies on biodiversity remain unrecognised or unquantified by individual businesses and other actors, despite the risk to businesses and society. Worldwide, the uptake of biodiversity policies in listed businesses has increased rapidly over the past two decades, supported by frameworks like those of the Global Reporting Initiative (GRI) and Taskforce on Nature-related Financial Disclosures (TNFD) (Combe et al., 2024), promoting actions towards dependency measurement. Still, evidence collated in this Chapter suggests that only an estimated 30 per cent of all sectors account for their dependence on biodiversity. Barriers include difficulty in measuring nature's contributions to people, low willingness to adopt biodiversity policies, lack of scientific environmental expertise in business, and lack of data and standardisation of dependency measurement (Bent et al., 2024).

² This Chapter uses both the terms nature's contributions to people and ecosystem services. The first is consistent with the IPBES framework; the latter is often used in academic studies as well as government and private sector reports.

There are many methods and metrics for quantifying dependencies and their values. Current methods include environmental-economic models, biophysical and ecological approaches, participatory monitoring and mapping approaches, monetary valuation methods, socio-cultural valuation methods, as well as integrated scenario analysis and synthesizing methods and socio-cultural valuation methods. Metrics range from contributions to product quality or quantity in volumes or hectares, to monetary values. While different methods and metrics capture the context-specificity of biodiversity and nature's contributions to people, the lack of standardisation complicates comparisons across options or across businesses, aggregating different dependencies, or understanding synergies, trade-offs and associated risks and opportunities. By effectively understanding and managing their dependencies on biodiversity, businesses can mitigate risks related to biodiversity loss, seize opportunities that support positive outcomes for biodiversity, society and the businesses themselves, and drive transformative change for sustainability and resilience in biodiversity, societies and economies.

To summarise the existing knowledge base, the authors of this chapter conducted a literature review.³ Initially, a snowball search of 20 papers yielded 1,934 publications, of which 151 papers were fully reviewed. Data was extracted on the type and magnitude of the dependency, sector and product, country and ecosystem, type of nature's contribution to people, and methods, metrics and data used, to assess the diversity and robustness of dependency assessments. A subsample was analysed to explore the magnitude of sectoral dependencies. The review was complemented with additional papers and expert analyses to ensure global coverage.

This chapter covers the following topics:

- Typology of dependencies, concepts of risks and magnitudes {2.2}
- Methods and approaches for assessing dependencies {2.3}
- Integrating methods, scenarios and metrics {2.4}
- Magnitude of dependencies and associated risks {2.5}
- Implications for society of business dependencies on nature {2.6}
- Implications for Indigenous Peoples and local communities (IPLCs) of business dependencies on nature {2.7}
- Trade-offs and synergies in dependencies {2.8}
- Knowledge gaps {2.9}

³ Data management report referring to the literature review conducted for Chapter 2
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2.2. Typology of dependencies

2.2.1. Characterizing dependencies of businesses on biodiversity

Businesses dependency on biodiversity varies and can be classified into direct dependencies at the level of business operations and dependencies through the value chain of a business. Operational dependencies involve natural assets or raw materials that a business requires for its production process like timber, water and medicinal and aromatic plants. For example, wood fibre is a direct physical input into paper production. Beyond material benefits, business operations also depend on biodiversity's regulating and non-material contributions that enable production or mitigate negative business impacts. For example, pollination enables food production and wetlands provide bioremediation of waste. Nature-based tourism highly depends on species richness or abundance, an example being wildlife recreational services in protected areas in Africa (Manley & Egoh 2024). Beyond direct dependency, businesses depend on biodiversity through the upstream value chain, sourcing products from other businesses that depend on biodiversity. Downstream in the value chain, they also depend on biodiversity, for instance for consumer product disposal and the treatment of waste, that relies on bio-based treatment technologies and nature's assimilative capacities.

Figure 2.1 illustrates operational level and values chain dependencies on biodiversity by sector (using International Standard Industrial Classification (ISIC) sector classification codes). For example, cotton farming operations depend on pollination, while the clothing factory operations depend on access to clean water, and through their value chain on pollination for cotton used in garment. Departments stores depend for their operations on flood regulation at store locations, and through their value chain on water and pollination for the manufacturing of the clothing they sell. This highlights that businesses across sectors have operational and value chain dependencies that come from all three categories of nature's contributions to people: material, regulation and non-material, both directly at operational level and through the value chain. While this chapter uses classification based on nature's contributions to people, ecosystem service terminology is common in business reporting.

Figure 2.1. The characterization of business dependencies on nature’s contributions to people (NCP). Shown through a conceptual example of different sectors in the clothing value chain. The codes indicate the ISIC sector classifications.

Various scientific and business publications and initiatives describe business dependency from operational and value chain perspectives. The Exploring Natural Capital Opportunities, Risks and Exposure database (ENCORE, n.d.) characterises operational dependencies through dependency pathways, with value chain dependencies arising from upstream trade links (dependence on economic activities in the value chain) and downstream in the value chain (consumption of outputs of direct operations by other economic sectors).

Business dependency and impact on biodiversity are closely linked. Negative impacts degrade ecosystems, reducing the stock of natural capital and the flow of benefits businesses rely on. For example, business dependency on water becomes a business impact if ecosystems or resources are not used or extracted sustainably (see **Section 2.2.2**). **Chapter 3** of this assessment explores these impacts further. To showcase the diversity of dependencies that can occur throughout the value chain, **Table 2.1.** provides examples of business dependencies from across the world.

Table 2. 1. Examples of business dependencies on biodiversity across the world.

Value chain stage	Dependency examples
Raw material	<p>Redlich et al. (2018) demonstrate that increasing crop diversification at landscape levels can improve bio pest control and thus possibly reduce the use of insecticides and enhance crop productivity in Germany.</p> <p>Karp & Daily (2014) find that insectivorous birds and bats significantly reduced non-flying arthropod abundance by 35 per cent and 25 per cent, causing cascading consequences for coffee plantations in Costa Rica. For instance, bird-mediated control of herbivores is seen as a long-term prevention of pest outbreaks.</p> <p>Cassol & Sellitto (2020) show that in the beauty and personal care industry, biodiversity is integral to sourcing natural ingredients like oils, plant extracts, and minerals in Brazil. Many of these ingredients are derived from plant and animal species, each contributing distinct chemical compounds essential for product formulation.</p>
Design, production and manufacturing of goods and services	<p>Biomimicry represents technology and design inspired by biodiversity; Lurie-Luke (2014) states that innovations in materials research account for 50 per cent of biomimicry studies globally.</p> <p>Zander et al. (2015) show that climate regulation services help mitigate direct impacts on production by limiting productivity losses from heat stress in Australia.</p> <p>Reddy et al. (2015) describe the financial effect of reliable water availability and water-use rights on the operations of a chemical company in the United States of America.</p> <p>Hadji-Lazaro et al. (2023) show dependencies on water for manufacturing and mining in South Africa, including employment in these sectors.</p>
Distribution and sales	<p>Transportation businesses depend on road infrastructure that benefits from biodiversity-driven soil retention and erosion control. Healthy plant and root systems in diverse ecosystems help prevent soil erosion, which maintains road durability and reduces maintenance costs. Hochard et al. (2019) show that mangroves protect economic activity from the effects of tropical cyclones, preventing permanent losses in 22 countries across the tropics.</p>
Consumption, use and repair	<p>Cardinale (2011) describes how clean water is preserved by biodiversity-rich ecosystems that filter and purify water sources through complex biological interactions, based on commonly found algal species in North America</p>
Collection, recycling and disposal	<p>Review studies by Bosch et al. (2019), Huis (2013), and Junge et al. (2023) show that insects can consume and decompose the waste and, in return, are a protein source that enables the feeding of livestock without requiring high technical knowledge nor space. Similarly, black shoulder flies are increasingly used in recycling waste, and so are bivalve molluscs and algae for water purification.</p> <p>Researchers use DSI to improve the efficiency and effectiveness of waste management. Singh and Shyu (2024) describe how the profiling of microbial community can be used in solid waste management.</p>

2.2.2. Magnitude of dependency

To manage dependencies, businesses need to assess (a) the quantity of material or non-material use of biodiversity, (b) the state of biodiversity (stock) and changes therein, and (c) the benefit flow from biodiversity and changes therein; ideally translated into business costs and benefits (TNFD, 2023b). Measuring use and tracking stock and flow changes are key for risk assessment (see **Section 2.2.4**).

Biodiversity dependencies vary across sectors and countries. Agriculture depends heavily on water, but water savings and requirements vary across crops, with rice needing more water than most crops (Cao et al., 2022). The information and communication technology sector relies on water for cooling, with 57 per cent of their cooling systems using potable water in some cases (Mytton, 2021), competing with other water uses. Businesses also vary in the type of nature's contributions to people they depend on. An assessment by the Finance for Biodiversity Foundation of the Morgan Stanley Capital International All Country World Index (MSCI ACWI) found that most businesses depend on surface and ground water and erosion control. **Section 2.5** provides further evidence.

Countries, business and finance entities are increasingly accounting for dependencies (see **Section 2.5**). Governments use the internationally agreed System of Environmental Economic Accounting – Ecosystem Accounting (SEEA-EA) framework to link the economy and environment with national accounts. At global and financial portfolio level, multiple studies have used the ENCORE database (ENCORE, n.d.), which provides qualitative scores of sectoral dependencies. These analyses show high dependencies for agriculture, forestry, fishery and aquaculture, as do related sectors (food, beverages and tobacco). Dependencies are also significant for the construction sector, utilities, communications, energy, industry and basic materials (Carvalho et al., 2023a).

2.2.3. Dependencies related to spatial and temporal scales

Businesses dependencies vary over space and time, influenced by spatial flows of nature's contributions to people (Kleemann et al., 2020), temporal aspects like seasonality (Del Río-Mena et al., 2020), and storage options (Willemen, 2020). Spatial flows include biophysical flows (e.g., downstream water regulation benefits), species movement (e.g., pollinators for agriculture, migratory species for hunting), material transport (e.g., trade, foraging), or information flow (e.g., learning from species, artistic inspiration, mental wellbeing and joy from distant landscape) (Bagstad et al., 2013; Schröter et al., 2018; Sitotaw Molla et al., 2024).

Business dependency involves all types of spatial flows, but trade-related dependencies are the most documented. Trade connects distal production systems along the value chain worldwide, in what is often called tele-coupling over long distances, or meta-coupling in adjacent areas (J. Liu et al., 2013) (See **Box 2.1**). Traded products depend on biodiversity in their region of origin, especially in agricultural, forestry and fisheries (A. Marques et al., 2024). Other spatial dependencies include pest control by migratory bird species (e.g., migration routes from the Great African Rift and the Savanna Zone to Germany) (Kleemann et al., 2020); tourism relying on cross-boundary wildlife migrations, and fisheries depending on surrounding fish populations. Understanding dependencies across scales can furthermore highlight power asymmetries and potential trade-offs or synergies (Martín-López et al., 2019).

Temporal dependency refers to variations in business dependency on biodiversity over years and seasons (e.g., tourist season, crop flowering period, erosion regulation and weather) and whether services can be stored (e.g., materials, food, water). Rau et al. (2020) identify three types of temporal patterns of ecosystem services: 1) long-term linear dependency (e.g., forestry logging, carbon storage in carbon credit schemes); 2) periodic dependency, where ecosystem services buffer climate or other

shocks (e.g., climate and water regulation for livestock during droughts); and 3) sudden, non-linear changes.

While spatial and temporal dependencies are well known, very few studies analyse them in detail.⁴ One area where dependences have been studied is for pollinators within natural vegetation in proximity to crop fields. Methodological challenges include data collection (e.g., tracking species or trade flows), capturing dependency variations (e.g., long- vs. short-term appropriation), and linking nature-related dependency assessments to business tools (e.g., integrating geospatial models with cost-benefit analyses to quantify temporal and spatial dependencies).

Large knowledge gaps and data constraints remain in quantifying spatial and temporally explicit dependencies. Methods to better disentangle the contributions of natural and human input to a production process need to become more spatially and temporally detailed.

Box 2.1. Dependencies in geographically distant regions for pollination services

Operational dependency: Reliance on pollination services varies across agricultural products. For instance, soybeans have a modest dependency on pollination (0.25 on a 0-1 scale), contributing 10–40 per cent to yields. Still, in Brazil, large-scale cultivation makes this economically significant (Giannini et al., 2015). In contrast, oleaginous crops like coconut, as well as perennial and non-perennial crops and berries, see less economic benefit (Figure 2.2, values from Giannini et al. (2015)⁵.

Figure 2.2. Economic benefits of pollination services in USD dollars for different crops and International Standard Industrial Classification subcategories in Brazil. The left column lists individual crops, while the middle column groups them into broader ISIC based categories. For instance, beans, broad beans, and cowpeas are classified under "legumes". The width of the grey lines indicates the magnitude of the economic benefits of pollination services. Data source: Giannini et al. (2015).

⁴ Data management report referring to the literature review conducted for Chapter 2
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12790967>

⁵ Details of the analysis are provided in the accompanying data management report
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17239488>

Value chain dependency: Many globally traded crops depend on nature's contributions to people. Approximately 50 per cent of traded crops rely on pollinators, with the majority originating from the Global South (Silva et al., 2021).

Figure 2.3. Virtual biotic pollination flow from South Africa (exporting country) to other countries from 2001 to 2015. “virtual biotic pollination” refers to the proportion of total crop production dependent on wild pollinators, while virtual biotic pollination flow represents the internationally traded portion of this pollination-dependent production (logarithmic colour coding highlights major flows) (Silva et al., 2021). This figure was reproduced from the Virtual Biotic Pollination Flow Tool Silva et al. (2021) and Lund University et al. (n.d.), which generates country-specific maps for selected years or for all years based on FAO’s trade matrix dataset (Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations (FAO), 2024).

2.2.4. Business risks from dependencies

Nature-related dependencies reflect businesses’ reliance on healthy ecosystems, while biodiversity -related risks arise from ecosystem degradation and biodiversity loss, impacting financial performance through higher operational costs and increased vulnerability to supply chain disruptions (Mandle et al., 2024). Similar to climate-related risks, biodiversity -related risks include physical, transition, and systemic risks (NGFS, 2024). *Physical* risks stem from ecosystem degradation and resulting loss of nature’s contributions to people, affecting economic activity (TNFD, 2025), directly linking biodiversity loss to business financial performance. In 2020, global business representatives ranked biodiversity loss among the top five global economic risks (WEF, 2020b). *Transition* risks arise from market, economic, technology or regulatory changes transitioning towards sustainability. *Systematic* risks include non-linear and destabilising cascading effects on assets, health, production, world prices, and ecological and financial systems.

High levels of dependencies pose increasing risks to businesses as biodiversity’s stocks and flows continue to decline. Yet, these dependencies are often unrecognized in value chains and the enabling conditions of business activity (Dasgupta, 2021; Marques et al., 2024; (Davies and Martini 2023)). This fundamental lack of awareness of physical risks which sometimes precedes lack of implementation of sustainability policies, increases the potential to overuse biodiversity beyond its carrying capacity and replenishable limits, potentially causing systemic risks like local and global

food insecurity, land degradation or ecosystem collapse (IPBES, 2018; Willett et al., 2019). These impacts may also disrupt value chains (Klein et al., 2007; WEF, 2023).

The Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC) risk model, based on ISO 3100, disaggregates cause and effect into exposure, hazard, and vulnerability. An adaptation of this framework for nature dependencies is presented in **Figure 2.4**.

Figure 2.4. Conceptual framework for understanding risks from business dependencies on nature (based on concepts from IPCC, 2014: International Standards Organization, 2018; and TNFD, 2023a).

In this framing:

- Risk is the consequence of a change in the availability of nature's contributions to people, and is determined by exposure, hazard and vulnerability
- Hazard results from changes in availability of nature's contributions to people. These changes can have natural causes, e.g., water availability may vary with seasons, but more often these can be human induced (IPBES, 2019b).
- Exposure to changes in the availability of nature's contributions to people in space and time can manifest both in an organization's operational activities (e.g., water use for irrigation) as well as any point in the value chain (e.g., sourcing of irrigated crops)
- Vulnerability is the degree to which a business is susceptible to, or unable to cope with, adverse effects of changes in availability of nature's contributions to people due to the decline of natural capital. For example, several sectors are highly vulnerable to water stress, including agriculture, manufacturing, and energy (Davies & Martini, 2023). Vulnerability has two components: dependency and adaptive capacity.
- Dependency is the degree to which a business requires the use of a specific nature's contributions to people or natural capital stock, either directly or through trade in the value chain (See **Section 2.2.2**). The ability to satisfy dependencies relies on the state of natural capital – both the stocks and the flows.

- Adaptive capacity is the ability of organizations to adjust to the consequences of loss of nature's contributions to people. Adaptation can reduce *vulnerability* and create *opportunities* (positive outcomes) for organizations by:
 - *Changing exposure* – such as relocating production, considering suppliers or portfolio constituents operating in locations with lower exposure to hazards, or considering the storage of nature's contributions to people if possible.
 - *Changing dependency* – such as substituting nature's contributions to people (e.g., artificial pest control), considering alternative products (e.g., dry shampoo in water-stressed markets), or supporting suppliers to increase the resilience of their operations. Evaluation of opportunities related to reducing dependency on nature's contributions to people via technological solutions should be evaluated also in terms of trade-offs and unintended consequences (Persson et al., 2022).
 - *Changing hazard* – such as by reducing human impacts on biodiversity, and/or investing in ecosystem restoration measures and nature-based solutions to enhance the state of natural capital to secure availability of nature's contributions to people. For example, investing in forest resilience bonds that enhances water supply (Madeira & Gartner, 2018).

Nature-related risks stem from natural capital scarcity, pressures causing stock and flow changes to decline, total demand (of business and other actors), and non-substitutability. Risk assessments must evaluate trends in natural capital, its availability, accessibility and substitutability. To identify risks, business and the financial sector use tools, such as risk scans, hotspot and scenario analyses (see **Sections 2.3 and 2.4**). The World Resources Institute's Corporate Ecosystem Services Review (ESR) helps businesses assess dependencies such as water regulation, pollination, and soil fertility (Hanson et al., 2012). By mapping services to business operations, businesses can identify critical 'pinch points'.

2.3. Methods and approaches for assessing dependencies

This section reviews methods and approaches for assessing nature-related dependencies to inform sustainable resource management, by recognizing the connection to biodiversity in traded products, assessing risks and vulnerabilities, value chain uncertainties and resilience (A. Marques et al., 2024). Methods and approaches are categorised into environmental-economic models, biophysical and ecological approaches, participatory monitoring and mapping, monetary valuation methods, and socio-cultural valuation methods. Each method and approach have varying scientific uptake, robustness, and industry application. **Table 2.2** summarises their robustness, reliability, and uptake. **Section 2.4** describes complementary approaches to integrate methods, analyse scenarios, and metrics and indicators.

2.3.1. Environmental-economic models

Economic models integrated with environmental models or indicators assess economy-nature interactions for screening and comparing options. Methods include: (a) (partial) equilibrium and integrated models, and (b) ecological-economic modelling.

- (a) (Partial) equilibrium and integrated models (macro): Integrated Assessment Models like the Integrated Model to Assess the Global Environment (IMAGE), partial equilibrium models like the Global Biosphere Management (GLOBIOM) model, and computable general equilibrium models like the Global Trade Analysis Project (GTAP) model, which use multi-regional input output tables like EXIOBASE, study trade-influenced emissions, impacts and competition of land at macro, i.e., high spatial, levels (regional-global), but also inputs and dependencies. Applications include Water-Energy-Food and circular economy assessments (Banerjee et al., 2020; Castelli et al., 2024; McCarthy et al., 2018).
- (b) Ecological-economic modelling (micro): Ecological-economic models are built more from a local level to analyse general environment-economy interactions in land use systems, such as the dependence of agriculture on biodiversity (Drechsler et al., 2022), aiming to include feedbacks and dynamics (Lawler et al., 2014). Other studies combine economic models with ecological or hydrological models to assess single or multiple nature's contributions to people and their values. These are sometimes scaled up to (sub-) national levels (or beyond) in spatially differentiated assessments (Bateman et al., 2013; Johnson et al., 2023). Some studies combine macro-economic models with more micro-level, spatial ecosystem models to demonstrate that the interactions and feedbacks between economic markets and policy and nature mean that nature loss produces economic loss, but also that nature investments pay off economically (Johnson et al., 2023).

Robustness and uptake of environment-economic approaches: These approaches have strong scientific underpinnings and can provide systemic, economy-wide perspectives on dependencies and risks, especially when linking environmental and economic accounts (e.g., System of Environmental Economic Accounting – Ecosystem Accounting - SEEA-EA) or applying computable general equilibrium frameworks (Banerjee et al., 2020; Zimmer et al., 2023). The robustness of macro-level models lies in the integration of multi-sector, multi-regional datasets and the ability to simulate counterfactuals under alternative policy or management scenarios. However, their uptake in the private sector remains limited because most applications operate at national or global scales and lack the sectoral granularity, site-specific ecological data, and product-level resolution required for corporate decision-making. Where used, they have primarily informed national accounting, strategic environmental assessment, and large-scale resource management. The more micro-level, local models, if based on site-specific ecological and economic data, has high relevance for business, but

most applications are currently not tailored to the needs of businesses. Wider adoption will require improved access to high-resolution trade, value chain, and biophysical datasets, and closer collaboration between modelers, industry, and statistical agencies to align outputs with corporate reporting needs.

2.3.2. Biophysical and ecological approaches

Biophysical approaches quantify the direct, physical relationships between business operations and biodiversity, using ecological data, spatial analysis, and modelling to trace business dependency on ecosystem functions (MEA 2005). Methods include: (a) location-based observations, (b) life cycle approaches, and (c) spatial analysis. Results from biophysical and ecological approaches are usually reported using metrics such as volume (e.g., volume of water), land areas in hectares and tonnes (e.g., crops produced).

- (a) Location-based observations, field surveys and remote sensing: Field-based ecological methods can be used to measure the abundance, stock and flow of nature's contributions to people and biodiversity and are useful for screening risks, comparing options and interventions, tracking progress and demonstrating impact, primarily at site-scale and for value chain analysis. A commonly used field-based method is the survey of species richness through capturing of bees to understand its impact on pollination and associated crop yield in volumes or quality. At higher spatial scales, remote sensing data can be used to map land use and land cover changes with high spatial coverage.
- (b) Life cycle approaches, life cycle assessments and biodiversity foot printing: Life cycle approach-based methods assess biodiversity dependencies and impacts across value chains by quantifying reliance on ecosystem functions, mainly for water, land, materials and energy. However, links to natural capital and supply changes are less established (Rugani et al., 2019). Integrating ecosystem service supply and demand into Life Cycle Assessments helps evaluate unsustainable use and nature-dependency risks (Liu et al., 2020) and extends the International Organization for Standardization (ISO) definitions of Life Cycle Assessments to quantify nature-enhancing business activities such as nature-based solutions (Alshehri et al., 2023). Biodiversity footprinting adds species loss or ecosystem degradation metrics but focuses on impacts rather than dependencies (Chaudhary & Brooks, 2018; Institute for European Environmental Policy, 2021). These rigorous and data-intensive methods benefit from well-established Life Cycle Assessment frameworks but may lack context-explicit reliability.
- (c) Spatial analysis, biophysical and ecological models: These methods use spatial data and ecological models to map biodiversity elements (e.g., habitat extent, species populations), natural capital stocks and benefit flows that businesses depend on. They often intersect with environmental risk mapping and focus on the supply of nature's contributions to people rather than the demand of the economy. Robustness comes from scientific models (e.g., species distribution, hydrological models). These methods allow for screening risk and comparing different strategies or project changes under different scenarios.

Robustness and uptake of biophysical and ecological approaches: Biophysical and ecological approaches enjoy substantial scientific uptake due to their quantitative biodiversity and strong ecological foundation. They offer robust and replicable results, thanks to clear ecological cause-effect linkages, with high reliability when quality data are available. However, data collection cost, especially in remote regions or for less-studied species, can create data gaps, limiting accuracy and coverage. Field surveys and experiments provide context-specific data and analysis but are costly for long-term monitoring. Dependency assessment remains less developed than impact assessment and requires refinement (Finance for Biodiversity Foundation, 2024; Gallai et al., 2009).

2.3.3. Participatory monitoring and mapping methods

Participatory methods can be used in collaboration with stakeholders - both in the value chain and those who have a direct interest or stake in biodiversity on which business depends – for different reasons, from corporate responsibility to legitimacy and to co-design (Hoes et al., 2021). Methods included here in their application vary in the extent to which they are defined, designed and conducted by citizens and community members: (a) participatory mapping & co-assessment with communities, (b) Indigenous and local knowledge-based indicators and monitoring, and (c) rights-based & ethical biocultural evaluations.

We include under this header also approaches supported by Indigenous Peoples that integrate Indigenous and local knowledge, community-led monitoring, and co-management practices to assess biodiversity dependencies. They ensure business assessments include traditional knowledge and community-defined indicators (Tengö et al., 2014). These approaches are increasingly recognized by global platforms (IPBES, 2019) and businesses operating nearby Indigenous territories.

- (a) Participatory mapping and co-assessment: Businesses and citizens jointly map biodiversity and nature's contributions to people, blending scientific data with traditional and local spatial knowledge. This co-assessment identifies biodiversity components and pressures on habitats that are critical for both business operations and community well-being and can be used to co-created strategies for sustaining livelihoods and biodiversity. Methods may include oral approaches such as storytelling and community dialogues, as well as visual approaches such as geographic information systems, mental mapping, and eco-cultural calendars (Robinson et al., 2016; Tengö et al., 2021).
- (b) Indigenous and local knowledge-based indicators and monitoring: Many IPLCs use indicators derived from traditional knowledge, such as seasonal indicators to monitor ecosystem health. Businesses can collaborate with communities to use these Indigenous and local knowledge indicators to gauge their resource dependencies, and involve local communities in collecting data through citizen-based approaches, in some countries recognized as citizen science (Danielsen et al., 2014).
- (c) Rights-based & ethical biocultural evaluations: These approaches emphasise respecting Indigenous values and rights, and also other applicable rights of local communities, using ethical dialogues and impact assessments. Aligning biodiversity management with local worldviews – for instance around resource use in mining and biotrade industries – benefits businesses through ethical sourcing, reduced conflicts, and stronger social licenses to operate.

Robustness and uptake of participatory monitoring and mapping methods: Involving citizens, IPLC members in mapping and monitoring dependencies ensures contextual validity and high local robustness. However, they are highly site-specific and lack universal metrics. Especially in the context of Indigenous Peoples, the application of these methods is guided by principles of reciprocity, spirituality and stewardship (Termansen et al., 2022). Therefore, their reliability depends on strong partnerships, trust, and genuine community engagement (Sterling et al., 2017). In some practical applications, genuine involvement of, and fair sharing of benefits with, IPLCs has been limited (Termansen et al., 2022). Scientific uptake of participatory mapping and monitoring approaches is increasing ((Berkes, 2012; Gómez-Baggethun & Barton, 2013) but uptake of results of participatory and co-production processes in decision-making remains limited (Turnhout et al., 2020).

2.3.4. Monetary valuation methods

Monetary valuation methods translate biodiversity dependencies into monetary metrics, aiding business decisions on costs, benefits, and risks. Originally from environmental economics (Dasgupta, 2021; TEEB, 2012a), they support corporate sustainability by assessing biodiversity degradation or enhancement impacts on productivity, profitability, and investment decisions. Common methods include (a) cost-based valuation, (b) revealed preference approaches, (c) market price methods, (d) stated preference methods, and (e) benefit transfer. These are useful for ex-ante comparisons or ex-post impact tracking in societal value terms.

- (a) Cost-based valuation methods: Cost-based methods estimate the economic value of biodiversity by examining the costs a business or sector would incur if nature's contributions to people were lost or degraded as they would need to invest in costly technological or engineered solutions. These include replacement cost (the expense of substituting or restoring an ecosystem function), damage cost avoided (the damages averted by preserving nature's contributions to people) and mitigation cost approaches. These methods provide lower-bound value estimates if replacement action has been implemented (see also Freeman III et al. 2014).
- (b) Revealed preference methods: Revealed preference methods, especially hedonic pricing and travel cost techniques, draw on actual market behaviours to infer the value of nature's contributions to people. By looking at how consumers spend money or how property prices differ in relation to environmental attributes, businesses can gauge how much biodiversity contributes to economic outcomes (Gibbons et al., 2014; Zhang et al., 2015).
- (c) Market price methods: Market price methods use observable prices in existing goods markets (e.g., agricultural commodities, fisheries, water trading) to assess how changes in biodiversity or nature's contributions to people affect supply, demand, and overall market dynamics. Specifically, production function approaches, factor income and bioeconomic modelling are useful in the context of assessing dependencies and valuing resource inputs in monetary terms. If nature's contributions to people are closely tied to the quantity or quality of a traded good, fluctuations in supply levels can be partly reflected in market prices.
- (d) Stated preference methods: Stated preference techniques – such as contingent valuation and choice experiments – collect primary data and elicit how much individuals would be willing to pay (or accept) for changes in nature's contributions to people under hypothetical market scenarios. Businesses can use these methods to capture non-market values (e.g., cultural identity, brand goodwill) that consumers, employees, or communities associate with biodiversity, and can inform the design of taxes or incentives schemes by providing insight into citizen and consumer preferences (TEEB, 2012a).
- (e) Benefit transfer methods: Benefit transfer (also called value transfer) involves adapting existing valuation estimates from one context (the 'study site') to inform decisions in a different but similar context (the 'policy or business site'). This can be especially useful when time or resources for primary valuation are limited.

Robustness and uptake of monetary valuation methods: Monetary valuation methods robustly translate biodiversity dependencies into financial metrics, aiding corporate strategy and reporting (Dasgupta, 2021; TEEB, 2012a). Their reliability hinges on data quality and valuation assumptions, which may oversimplify ecological interdependencies (Pascual et al., 2017). Scientific scrutiny and uptake are considerable. While cost- and market-based methods may overlook cultural or spiritual values, combining them with biophysical and socio-cultural approaches strengthens biodiversity dependency assessments within economic frameworks.

2.3.5. Socio-cultural valuation methods

Socio-cultural valuation methods capture the cultural, spiritual, or heritage values of biodiversity dependencies through the lens of human values, preferences, and cultural significance (Scholte et al., 2015). They are increasingly recognized in business sustainability assessments for brand identity or customer goodwill. Common methods include: (a) expert elicitation, (b) participant observation, (c) document analysis, (d) perception assessments, and (e) narrative assessments.

- (a) Expert elicitation, Delphi and Q-method: These methods rely on relatively small samples of well-informed stakeholders to provide information about complex and uncertain topics, such as the importance of nature's contributions to people and biodiversity, the implications of dependencies and the effects of risk management. These methods are suitable when there is a lack of data, or when collecting data is prohibitively expensive. While expert elicitation and Delphi techniques are consensus oriented, Q-methods aim to explore subjectivity and variation in opinions.
- (b) Participant observation: For this method, a researcher engages in a particular social setting or group, observing the behaviours, interactions, and practices of the participants to understand the experiences of individuals or groups which are value expressions. Businesses can use these assessments to reinforce brand identity and ensure sustainable supply chain practices.
- (c) Document analysis: This method extracts information about perceptions of dependencies from existing documentation, and is often used to study the enabling environment, including policy frameworks, but can also be used to identify the values of different stakeholders, for instance using media analysis.
- (d) Perception assessments: Businesses can use different types of ranking exercises, or photo-elicitation methods to engage stakeholders (employees, customers, local communities) to understand which nature's contributions to people and biodiversity are perceived as most important, thereby revealing co-dependencies, synergies and trade-offs. These methods often involve larger samples and (semi-) quantitative analysis.
- (e) Narrative methods: These methods provide qualitative data on dependencies and values of nature's contributions to people and biodiversity using focus groups, storytelling, workshops, and interviews (Reed, 2008). They can be used to assess experienced changes over time and space, trade-offs and synergies, and provide context-specific data on dependencies.

Robustness and uptake of socio-cultural valuation methods: Socio-cultural valuation methods offer context-specific insights, with reliability depending on stakeholder representativeness and toll design (e.g., formal vs. informal feedback). Robustness improves with systematic frameworks such as Delphi surveys (Mukherjee et al., 2015). These methods vary in skills, time, and budget required. Scientific uptake is growing in interdisciplinary fields such as ecological economics and sustainability science. They provide insights that are critical for developing business initiatives that are both culturally sensitive and conservation-oriented (Chan et al., 2012), as they capture relational and shared values (Intergovernmental Science-Policy Platform on Biodiversity and Ecosystem Services et al., 2022) essential for comprehensive dependency assessments but often overlooked (Pascual et al., 2017).

Table 2.2. Selected and additional examples of business dependencies on biodiversity across key methodological approaches. The table also presents associated references and assessment of scientific uptake, reliability and resource requirements.

Approach and sub-method	Example of dependency	Scientific uptake, reliability, & resource requirements
Environmental-economic models		
Equilibrium and integrated models	<p>Alaskan tourism operators benefit from Steller sea lion protection; a Computable General Equilibrium model captures how shifts in wildlife conservation alter resource allocation and economic flows across industries (Finnoff & Tschirhart, 2008).</p> <p>Using a general equilibrium model, the agricultural dependency on pollination is estimated to be considerable and outweigh the abatement costs of several measures to protect pollinators in multiple European countries (Zimmer et al., 2023).</p>	<p>Scientific uptake: Relatively advanced; mostly in academic or specialized consulting contexts.</p> <p>Reliability: High for system-level insights but sensitive to model assumptions.</p> <p>Resources: Requires robust data across economics, ecology, and social factors; can be computationally intensive.</p>
Ecological-economic modelling	<p>A spatially explicit model was used to find land allocation solutions for Oregon, USA, that sustain high levels of biodiversity as well as economic revenue (Polasky et al., 2008).</p> <p>Regulating nature’s contributions to people, such as drought control from tropical forests, supporting nearby agricultural producers by preventing drought events (Pattanayak & Kramer, 2001).</p>	<p>Scientific uptake: Established in policy and academic domains, limited in corporate applications.</p> <p>Reliability: High for macro-style insights; moderate for firm-level decisions without downscaling.</p> <p>Resources: Requires multi-disciplinary expertise and access to linked environmental-economic and trade datasets.</p>
Biophysical and ecological approaches		
Location-based observations: Field surveys	<p>Family farms depend on consistent rainfall and healthy soils for key staple crops (maize, millet, rice) in tropical regions (e.g., Brazil, Senegal, Vietnam) (Affholder et al., 2013)</p> <p>Primary data from smallholder farms in Colombia was used to assess how natural pollination affects coffee fruit set. The combination with monetary valuation showed that losing native bees would cost \$16.5/ha and losing honeybees would cost \$129.6/ha (Bravo-Monroy et al., 2015).</p> <p>Remote sensing can help identify both impacts and dependencies of dairy farming (Reid & Castka, 2023)</p> <p>Small-scale farmers and fisherfolks use visual surveys to gauge species richness, evenness, and relative dominance (Nishi et al., 2025)</p>	<p>Scientific uptake: Common in agronomy, ecology, and environmental management.</p> <p>Reliability: Moderate to high, contingent on representative sampling and robust survey design.</p> <p>Resources: Requires trained field teams and adequate time for data collection.</p>
Spatial analysis: spatial mapping	<p>The acreage of medicinal plant resources (e.g., for Traditional Chinese Medicine) was identified and classified to illustrate industry dependence</p>	<p>Scientific uptake: Broadly used in environmental/land-use studies;</p>

	<p>on specific plant habitats and ecosystem productivity (Meng et al., 2023).</p> <p>Geospatial mapping of seagrass beds, using satellite imagery and spatial models to quantify their global distribution, to assess the vulnerability of coastal fisheries to habitat loss, showed that rapid seagrass declines – critical nursery habitats for many fish species – can significantly reduce juvenile fish survival and stock sustainability, jeopardizing the long-term productivity of coastal fisheries (Waycott et al., 2009).</p>	<p>remote sensing widely accepted for spatial inventories.</p> <p>Reliability: High, given suitable satellite/imaging data and ground truthing.</p> <p>Resources: Data-intensive; software and technical expertise needed.</p>
<p>Spatial analysis: biophysical models</p>	<p>Vineyards depend on suitable climatic and soil conditions, and machine-learning models project shifting areas for grape cultivation in Europe, highlighting the wine sector’s reliance on biodiversity-driven ecosystem processes (Moriondo et al., 2013).</p> <p>Coastal flood models and coral reef maps measure how coral ecosystems protect insured coastal assets from storm surges with the potential to inform insurance industry risk models (Beck et al., 2018).</p>	<p>Scientific uptake: Strong within climate change and agricultural modelling communities.</p> <p>Reliability: Dependent on model calibration and input data quality.</p> <p>Resources: Requires expertise in modelling software, climate/ ecological datasets.</p>
<p>Life cycle approaches</p>	<p>Dependency of rice production systems on water provisioning, as well as dependencies on carbon sequestration, water quality, and air quality regulation (Liu et al., 2020).</p>	<p>Scientific uptake: Proof-of-concept application in academic case studies, no wider uptake by business.</p> <p>Reliability: Highly dependent on quality and regional representativeness of input data, often not spatially explicit.</p> <p>Resources: Data intensive; requires interdisciplinary knowledge and incorporation of specialist modelling. No operationalization in Life Cycle Assessment software.</p>
<p>Participatory monitoring and mapping methods</p>		
<p>Participatory mapping & co-assessment</p>	<p>Local fishing communities, as key IPLCs stakeholders, collaborated with researchers to map and assess fisheries, revealing how artisanal fishing businesses depend on healthy coastal and mangrove habitats (Sagoe et al., 2021).</p> <p>In Tun Mustapha Park, IPLCs joined forces with a mariculture enterprise to co-map essential marine nature’s contributions to people and demonstrate their shared reliance on healthy reefs and mangroves, guiding more inclusive and</p>	<p>Scientific uptake: Widely used in social sciences, increasing use in IPLCs research and practice.</p> <p>Reliability: High-context specificity, integration of knowledge systems can be complicated.</p> <p>Resources: Considerably resource-intensive to ensure ethical and non-extractive</p>

	sustainable resource management in the region (Lim et al., 2021).	practices; requires mutual training and field travel.
Indigenous and local knowledge-based indicators and monitoring	<p>The Athabasca Landing Métis Community partnered with the oil sands industry to design a community-based monitoring program that merges Indigenous knowledge (e.g., hunting and foraging traditions) with scientific tools (like geo-referenced photo mapping) to track biodiversity and environmental changes, providing early warnings and promoting sustainable resource use (O’Connor et al., 2022).</p> <p>The Gitga’at First Nation co-developed a biodiversity monitoring program with external researchers that integrates Indigenous knowledge (e.g., local observations of fish, shellfish, and marine mammals) with scientific methods to track ecosystem health, safeguarding vital subsistence and economic resources for communities and external stakeholders in tourism and fisheries (Thompson et al., 2019).</p>	<p>Scientific uptake: Increasing use in community-based research and practice.</p> <p>Reliability: High-context specificity, integration of knowledge systems can be complicated.</p> <p>Resources: Considerably resource-intensive to ensure ethical and non-extractive practices; requires mutual training and field travel; data collection itself can be less costly.</p>
Rights-based & ethical biocultural evaluation	IPLCs in Colombia effectively applied a biocultural diversity framework to safeguard their knowledge systems through ethical, rights-based principles that respect traditional customs (Nemogá et al., 2022).	<p>Scientific uptake: Increasing use in community-based research and practice.</p> <p>Reliability: High-context specificity, integration of knowledge systems can be complicated.</p> <p>Resources: Considerably resource-intensive to ensure ethical and non-extractive practices; requires mutual training and field travel.</p>
Monetary valuation methods		
Cost-based methods	Downstream farmers in South India depend for irrigation on clean upstream water provided by upstream biodiversity that underpins natural filtration; replacement costs (e.g., damaged pump and filtration systems) illustrate how industrial pollution can threaten farm productivity (V. R. Reddy & Behera, 2006)	<p>Scientific uptake: Common in environmental economics for pollution control and resource management.</p> <p>Reliability: Straightforward if cost data are available; can oversimplify complex ecosystem functions resulting in higher uncertainties.</p> <p>Resources: Requires site-specific cost data and basic hydrological context.</p>
Revealed preference	Real estate businesses rely on biodiversity to maintain property values: house prices increase in proximity to scenic landscapes and wildlife	Scientific uptake: Well-established in environmental

	<p>presence in forests and wetlands, shown by hedonic pricing analyses (Fois et al., 2019)</p> <p>The value of Gold Coast recreational beach visits was estimated at \$117 million per year (AUD) for tourists and 402 million per year (AUD) for residents, using the travel cost method (Zhang et al., 2015)</p>	<p>economics, especially property value studies.</p> <p>Reliability: Low to moderate depending on data quality. Data-intensive (requires robust real market data).</p> <p>Resources: Statistical expertise, reliable real estate and biodiversity data.</p>
Market price methods	<p>Farmers in the Mississippi Basin depend on wetlands for nutrient regulation and water quality (reducing the need for costly fertilizers and mitigating runoff); market price models can reveal how wetland restoration and nitrogen credit trading affect agricultural commodity prices (Ribaudo et al., 2005).</p> <p>Based on the production function method, the value of soil retention and pollination services to agricultural values at regional and national level represents 44 per cent of the value of production (Grammatikopoulou et al., 2024)</p>	<p>Scientific uptake: Straightforward when a well-functioning market exists for a related good (e.g., farm. commodities).</p> <p>Reliability: High if causal pathways between biodiversity and market outcomes are established; may be confounded by subsidies or externalities.</p> <p>Resources: Data on prices, production volumes and ecosystem conditions and market dynamics (e.g., supply-and-demand models).</p>
Stated preference methods	<p>Ecotourism operators rely on healthy landscapes; contingent valuation or choice experiments reveal visitors’ willingness to pay for biodiversity conservation (e.g., iconic species, pristine habitats) (TEEB, 2012a)</p> <p>Different stated preference studies assess customer preferences for changes in water supply and environmental services and their willingness to pay for these – such payments can help recover costs of restoration of ecosystems that provide water supply and quality (Willis & Sheldon, 2022).</p>	<p>Scientific uptake: Widely used in environmental economics for non-market valuation.</p> <p>Reliability: Depends on survey design and the realism of hypothetical scenarios; prone to bias if not carefully structured.</p> <p>Resources: Social science expertise, representative sampling of stakeholders, and clear scenario framing to capture perceived value of biodiversity.</p>
Benefit transfer	<p>Farmers in the Mississippi Alluvial Valley use previously estimated nitrogen mitigation values from similar regions to evaluate the benefits of adjusting fertilizer usage or retiring cropland (Jenkins et al., 2010). This also provides businesses and policymakers with rapid, cost-effective insights into their dependence on services like water filtration and soil fertility.</p>	<p>Scientific uptake: A frequent, cost-effective approach in policy and corporate contexts when primary valuable is not feasible.</p> <p>Reliability: Varies with the similarity between the “study site” and “application site”, and the robustness of original valuation data.</p> <p>Resources: Access to relevant external studies, plus careful calibration to local ecological, economic and cultural conditions.</p>

Socio-cultural valuation methods		
Expert elicitation, Delphi & Q methods	<p>Chemical manufacturing depends on adequate freshwater availability; a Delphi-type approach estimated potential production losses if water supply declines (Reddy et al., 2015).</p> <p>Salmon aquaculture stakeholders in Tasmania were interviewed using a Q-method approach; findings suggest that they highly value seabed health and water quality to sustain the coastal ecosystem services that they rely on (Pethiyagoda et al., 2024)</p>	<p>Scientific uptake: Moderate but increasing, especially for complex ‘what-if’ scenarios in corporate planning.</p> <p>Reliability: Can be high if experts are diverse and iteration is well-structured.</p> <p>Resources: Facilitation, expert networks and iterative survey tools required.</p>
Participant observation	<p>A large environmental sector company recognizes direct reliance on biodiversity (e.g., pollination, pest control) through an embedded researcher’s on-site observations and staff interviews (Feger & Mermet, 2022)</p> <p>Participant observation in combination with other socio-cultural valuation methods reveal how botanical species in biodiverse regions like the Amazon, used in cosmetics, hold deep cultural significance for Indigenous communities (Iniesta-Arandia et al., 2014)</p>	<p>Scientific uptake: Less common in corporate contexts, more frequent in anthropological or organizational research.</p> <p>Reliability: Depends on researcher’s access and objectivity.</p> <p>Resources: Time-intensive, interpretation and analysis can be difficult.</p>
Document analysis	<p>Document analysis demonstrated that the enabling policy framework for hydropower in Nepal does not yet consistently and comprehensive include nature’s contributions to people (Lohani Sitoula et al., 2024).</p> <p>Document analysis revealed that conflicts arise over provisioning nature’s contributions to people due to high competition, with power imbalances shaping the outcomes in forestry in Turkiye (Başkent, 2022).</p>	<p>Scientific uptake: Widely used in social sciences research.</p> <p>Reliability: Moderate to high. Data may be limited, and reliability depends on transparency in process and triangulation.</p> <p>Resources: Not very resource intensive.</p>
Perception assessments	<p>Results of 1,634 photograph-based interviews across Sweden, Latvia, Belarus and Russia captured how different people value agroforestry landscapes; agriculture and forestry enterprises managing land can integrate these diverse stakeholder values into decision-making (Elbakidze et al., 2021).</p>	<p>Scientific uptake: Widely used in social sciences, increasing use in applications on nature’s contributions to people.</p> <p>Reliability: Data quality hinges on sampling strategy and survey design.</p> <p>Resources: Moderately resource-intensive; requires interviewer training and possible field travel.</p>

<p>Narrative methods</p>	<p>Farming communities describe how wildlife (e.g., primates, ungulates) can damage crops, highlighting dependence on balanced local fauna and pest control (Hill, 1997).</p> <p>Interviews helped to understand how wine makers in Australia integrate nature’s contributions to people, such as water quantity, into their management (Sandhu et al., 2018).</p> <p>Interviews revealed the role of nature’s contributions to people in China’s forestry sector, finding that increased resource competition combined with increased frequency and unpredictability of natural hazards drive up dependency risks (Wan et al., 2017).</p> <p>Interviews were used to determine the credit risk of Australian beef cattle industry resulting from natural capital dependencies (Ascui & Cojoianu, 2019).</p>	<p>Scientific uptake: Widely used in social sciences.</p> <p>Reliability: Data quality hinges on sampling strategy and protocol design, and control of polarisation and power imbalances when applied in groups.</p> <p>Resources: Moderately resource-intensive; requires possible field travel.</p>
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2.4. Integrating methods, scenarios and metrics

The use of the methods described in **Section 2.3** often requires further analysis through integrating and synthesising methods, which allow for bringing together different dependencies assessment approaches into a joint analysis framework to support decision-making. We describe such methods in **Section 2.4.1**. Scenario analysis, described in **Section 2.4.2**, can further support decision-making and strategy development for managing business dependencies on nature by anticipating future risks, pathway development, and robust effectiveness assessment of interventions to manage dependencies. **Section 2.4.3** describes metrics and indicators that can be used in dependencies assessments to support decision-making, and that can be used in the integrating and synthesising methods of **Section 2.4.1**.

2.4.1. Integrated and synthesising methods

Following the IPBES Values Assessment (IPBES, 2022), biodiversity dependency assessments would ideally combine different methods to express these dependencies and their meaning in terms of endpoints of interest to people. Method combination is inherent to the integrated Environmental-Economic models described in **Section 2.3.1**, which combine ecological and economic data and methods. Monetary and socio-cultural valuation methods can build on biophysical research to assess how changes in biodiversity relate to changes in other types of values meaningful to stakeholders, and to changes in quality of life.

There are also methods and tools that combine values and indicators (derived through methods described in **Sections 2.3.1 - 2.3.5**) for a holistic assessment of biodiversity dependencies and interventions to address these, which we list here as Integrated and synthesising methods. Supported by frameworks such as the IPBES conceptual framework (Díaz et al., 2015) and The Economics of Ecosystems and Biodiversity for Business (TEEB, 2012a), they can use multiple criteria and interdisciplinary biophysical, economic, and socio-cultural metrics. These methods help to integrate the multiple effects that interventions to address biodiversity dependencies can have and help to prioritise these. Key methods include: (a) Multi-criteria decision analysis, (b) Cost-benefit analysis,

and (c) Natural capital assessment & accounting. These methods have high scientific uptake and adoption by businesses and financial institutions is growing. **Table 2.3** provides an overview.

- (a) Multi-criteria decision analysis: Multi-criteria decision analysis tools help businesses evaluate options or prioritize actions when multiple biodiversity dependency factors are at play, by incorporating ecological, social, and economic criteria (Kiker et al., 2005). By scoring and weighting different criteria, multi-criteria decision analysis provides a structured method to incorporate ecological metrics into industry decision-making to compare alternatives, such as sourcing locations or mitigation strategies (see Huang et al., 2011).
- (b) Cost-benefit analysis: Cost-benefit analysis compares the monetized benefits of maintaining or enhancing nature's contributions to people against the costs of conservation, restoration, or alternative provisioning through built capital. It is widely used in project appraisal and environmental policy evaluation (Freeman III et al., 2014; TEEB, 2012b). In a business context, cost-benefit analysis can quantify the net economic gains from actions such as watershed restoration to secure industrial water supplies, habitat conservation to sustain pollination services, or investment in green infrastructure to reduce flood risks. When combined with ecological models, social cost-benefit analysis can capture both market and selected non-market benefits, enabling businesses to identify investments that generate positive returns for both the company and broader society. Limitations include the difficulty of monetizing cultural and relational values, sensitivity to discount rates, and uncertainty in long-term ecological responses.
- (c) Natural capital assessment & accounting: This approach quantifies biodiversity and nature's contributions to people in economic terms, integrating biodiversity into business accounting (Dasgupta, 2021; Natural Capital Coalition, 2016). Using biophysical and monetary data, the System of Environmental-Economic Accounting Ecosystem Accounting - Ecosystem Accounting (SEEA-EA) framework contains both physical and economic accounts, including an assessment of the state of biodiversity, i.e., ecosystem extent and condition, and flows of ecosystem services, linked to economic accounts, but relies on exchange (market prices and cost) values. These methods are translated into business accounting standards (Capitals Coalition, 2022) to help businesses assess nature-related risks and identify more sustainable extraction practices. Business-oriented frameworks also emphasise links to other types of interlinked capital (human, produced, etc) (TEEB, 2018).

Robustness and uptake: Integrated methods are robust, and cross-validate economic valuations, ecological data, and socio-cultural methods as well as participatory mapping and monitoring information. While integration is complex due to issues of commensurability (especially in cost-benefit analysis), scientific uptake is strong. Leading businesses are piloting these methods, as researchers continue to refine them for improved decision support. As demand for comprehensive nature-related risk assessments grows, adoption is expected to rise (Addison et al., 2020; WEF, 2020a).

Table 2.3. Selected and additional examples of business dependencies on biodiversity across key methodological approaches. The table also presents associated references and assessment of scientific uptake, reliability and resource requirements

Integrated and synthesizing methods		
Multi-criteria decision analysis (MCDA)	<p>Fisheries enterprises depend on healthy fish stocks; Analytic Hierarchy Process reveals how stakeholders in the Bay of Biscay, the English Channel, and the North Sea, weigh ecological vs. economic objectives such as fish stock conservation, profitability, and social stability and highlight biodiversity as a driver of profit sustainability (Mardle et al., 2004).</p> <p>Participatory multi-criteria decision analysis involving industry players and stakeholders examined trade-offs between peat extraction businesses, climate regulation, water quality, and biodiversity in Finnish peatlands, revealing direct dependencies of peat-based businesses on peatland ecosystems and guiding more sustainable resource use (Saarikoski et al., 2019).</p>	<p>Scientific Uptake: Widely used in environmental decision-making for complex trade-offs.</p> <p>Reliability: High if stakeholder representation and criteria weighting are transparent.</p> <p>Resources: Requires facilitation, data on multiple criteria, and collaboration among stakeholders.</p>
Cost-benefit analysis	<p>Forest conservation in the Brazilian Amazon increases açai palm pollination services, improving yields and generating a positive net present value for local producers and supply-chain partners, which could be used to inform a cost-benefit analysis exercise (Campbell et al., 2023).</p>	<p>Scientific Uptake: Well-established in environmental economics; growing in corporate natural capital assessments.</p> <p>Reliability: Strong where biophysical changes can be reliably linked to economic outcomes; sensitive to valuation assumptions.</p> <p>Resources: Requires interdisciplinary expertise in economics, ecology, and valuation; moderate to high data demands.</p>
Natural capital accounting	<p>Natural capital accounting was used to determine the economic values of forest in Ethiopia using a welfare-economic framework that treats changes in forest stock as a form of capital accumulation or depreciation (Narita et al., 2018)</p> <p>Monetary valuation of groundwater stocks was used to value aquifer depletion, demonstrating how natural capital accounting can guide resource-intensive industries—especially agriculture—to incorporate ecosystem costs into risk management and investment decisions (Fenichel et al., 2016).</p>	<p>Scientific Uptake: Gaining traction, endorsed by frameworks like the Natural Capital Protocol.</p> <p>Reliability: Depends on ecological and economic data quality; can be technically demanding.</p> <p>Resources: Interdisciplinary expertise (finance, ecology, accounting) usually needed.</p>

2.4.2. Scenarios and counterfactuals

Scenarios support multi-stage decision-making by revealing dependencies and risks and expected effects of changes to natural capital from pressures, policies or business strategies. Using systems-thinking, they explore systemic risks to business. The IPBES Nature Futures Framework (IPBES, 2023) was specifically designed to support scenario development and provides an overview of existing scenario approaches. Here, “scenarios” refer to internally consistent, plausible descriptions of future conditions (e.g., biophysical, economic, and policy) used to explore “what-if” questions, test the robustness of strategies, identify thresholds or tipping points, or evaluate future impacts.

Scenarios can be qualitative (e.g., narratives co-developed with stakeholders) or quantitative (model-based projections of land use, climate, or market conditions), or both. Ex-ante and ex-post impact assessments require baselines and counterfactuals to establish causality and attribution; establishing baseline conditions allows comparisons across sectors, land uses (e.g., Baral et al., 2013), and management strategies aiding biodiversity-related decision-making. This enables business to better assess and manage risks by showing sensitivity of dependencies to shocks, trends, and policy pathways (Cheung et al., 2019; IPBES, 2023). For instance, (Cheung et al., 2019) used participatory approaches to model wild fish provisioning, showing that high-seas fishing is unprofitable without further measures in fisheries and conservation. However, the use of scenario analysis and long-term outlooks is rare and mostly limited to short-term shock assessments rather than longer-term dynamics (see **section 2.5.5**).

2.4.3. Metrics and indicators

Assessing dependencies requires multiple indicators and metrics for monitoring, evaluation and reporting. The Convention on Biological Diversity has adopted a state-pressure-response-benefit framework to guide indicator development for biodiversity (Burgess et al., 2024). While biodiversity impact indicators and metrics exist, a framework for monitoring and reporting on business dependencies on biodiversity and nature's contributions to people is largely absent. The Convention on Biological Diversity framework categorises all business dependencies under the benefit category “ecosystem services”. However, indicators such as business risk and response indicators, such as business action, should be considered (Addison et al., 2020).

As shown in **Section 2.2.4**, assessing dependencies requires metrics for both environmental and organizational contexts – how much biodiversity is available for sustainable use and how much is used in production (Smith et al., 2024). Methods described in **Section 2.3.1** generate various metrics covering these aspects. However, the few existing dependency indicators focus on benefits such as productivity, or risk related to magnitude of dependency.

Studies on dependencies and risks use various metrics and units, depending on methods and focus areas, such as natural capital stocks or flows of nature's contributions to people (demand/supply). Biophysical and ecological approaches are used most often and use quantitative productivity metrics such as fruit/crop yield or cattle yield in kilograms per hectare, volumes of water, or biodiversity metrics such as species richness/abundance, while qualitative metrics include product quality (e.g., of meat or fruit). Monetary valuation studies, second most used, report outcomes in local currency or international dollars, relating company output to biodiversity input. Integrated methods use both quantitative and qualitative units. Socio-cultural valuation methods also use both, from productivity increases to monetary values of increasing farm biodiversity to qualitative ratings of consumer preferences.

Indicators and metrics to monitor and report on dependencies remain unstandardised, but emerging regulatory pressure such as the European Union's Corporate Sustainability Reporting Directive is

pushing towards more standardisation in metrics and reporting standards (Giner & Luque-Vílchez, 2022). A review (Smith et al., 2024) of 349 assessed indicators found only 54 (15 per cent) directly measure dependencies, 33 (9 per cent) are proxy measures, and only 8 indicators (2 per cent) capture financial consequences of lost ecosystem services. Knowledge gaps persist in metrics linking financial impacts to nature risks, and in indicators enabling comparisons across geographies and industries (Smith et al., 2024). While biophysical indicators are common, socio-economic effects are less studied. This chapter’s literature review highlights this issue, with no crosscutting indicators and metrics that integrate business and biodiversity for monitoring purposes.

Figure 2.5 is based on the summary of selected studies from the snowball search⁶ exercise on water (A) and pollination (B). The snowball search exercise not only found that pollination dependencies were studied more often, but also that the pollination studies assessed a wider array of metrics, related to economic dependencies, production changes, quality changes and risk, compared to water-related dependencies which were expressed only in terms of productivity changes or risk.

Figure 2.5. The frequency of International Standard Industrial Classification subcategories studied for each metric used to measure the dependency. A) pollination services and B) water services.

⁶ A detailed explanation and comprehensive review of the process carried out for selecting the literature for this chapter can be found in the data management report <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12790967>

2.5. Magnitudes of dependencies and associated risks

This section summarises the academic evidence of the quantification of dependencies using a sub-sample of 151 articles selected from the snowball search,⁷ and demonstrates that dependencies are high and widespread across global ecosystems.

2.5.1. Magnitudes of dependencies at the global and regional level

Businesses depend on biodiversity, including genetic diversity, species, ecological functions and services. It has been estimated that \$ 44 to 58 trillion, or 50 to 55 per cent of global GDP, moderately or highly depends on ecosystem services (WEF & PWC, 2020, Retsa et al, 2020, PwC, 2023). For example, the agricultural sector heavily dependent on pollination services, which contribute about 30 per cent of global food production (Khalifa et al., 2021). Biotic pollination improves fruit and seed quality or quantity of 87 global crops (Khalifa et al., 2021), 70 per cent of 1330 tropical crops (Roubik & Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations, 1995), and 85 per cent of 264 European crops (Williams, 1994). Globally, pollinator-dependent crop areas grew 137 per cent from 1961 to 2016 (Aizen et al., 2019). The annual market value of the 5-8 per cent of production that is directly linked with pollination services is estimated at \$235 billion-\$577 billion (in 2015 US\$) worldwide (IPBES et al., 2016). Forests are another important source of inputs to production for timber, pharmaceutical and cosmetic industries. According to the Convention of Biological Diversity, over 80 per cent of registered medicines originate from plants or have been inspired by natural products (Bernardini et al., 2018) Water is another critical input to business. Approximately 42 per cent of the global workforce operates in water-dependent sectors (Sjöstrand et al., 2021; Unesco, 2016), such as construction, forestry, fisheries, and manufacturing. These inputs are often assessed using water footprinting methods. These methods assess the virtual trade in water, for instance highlighting that the 54 African countries, grouped into five main regions, are net importers of 40,000 Bm³ of virtual water from grain products from 2000 to 2020, mostly green water (79 per cent), especially in North Africa (Hirwa et al., 2022).

The European Union's ecosystem service accounts include multiple ecosystem services, including water purification and recreation, and value these at 228 EUR billion (**Figure 2.6**), though these accounts cover only terrestrial ecosystems. Coastal and marine ecosystems provide essential services for businesses, including food, raw materials, water purification, carbon sequestration, and recreation. Direct ocean outputs, such as marine fisheries, mangroves, coral reefs and sea grass, were valued at \$ 6.9 trillion in total gross value (Hoegh-Guldberg et al., 2015). Aquaculture is crucial to global food systems, with fish supplying 17 per cent of animal-based protein and 6.5 per cent of total protein consumed worldwide (Troell et al., 2014). Small-scale fishers contribute 40 per cent of global catches, supporting 1 in every 12 people's livelihoods (Basurto et al., 2025) and contributing approximately \$ 77.2 billion to the total economic value of global fisheries (Basurto et al., 2025). Coral reefs provide \$ 172 billion in value (OECD, 2022). Climate-related coral loss could cost tourism 1 - 2.89 billion \$ by 2050 under different climate change scenarios (P.-Y. Chen et al., 2015).

⁷ A detailed explanation and comprehensive review of the process carried out for selecting the literature for this chapter can be found in the data management report (10.5281/zenodo.12790967).

Figure 2.6. Flows between ecosystem services and economic sectors in the European Union. Data for 2018, sourced from (Joint Research Centre, European Commission, n.d.) accessed in February of 2024⁸.

Box 2.2. Microbes’ contribution to businesses

Microbial communities, or microbiomes, exist in every habitat on Earth and host tremendous genetic and metabolic diversity for industrial applications, especially in agricultural and energy. Digital sequencing information is extensively used in these sectors. Fungi and bacteria are essential in producing beer, wine, cheese, bread, and other fermented foods mostly using DSI. Industries increasingly harness microbes in agricultural and industrial processes from fields to factories, with businesses developing products that embody natural microbial benefits to assist plants in acquiring nutrients or avoiding pathogens, thereby reducing the need for pesticides and fertilisers. The global microbial bioinoculant market exceeded \$ 2.25 billion in 2023 (Fortune Business Insights, 2024).

Biofuel energy industries also rely on microbiomes. Ethanol production from corn or sugarcane, valued at \$ 90 billion per year globally, relies on bacterial fermentation in bioreactors (Skyquest, 2024). Emerging biofuel and bioproduct strategies focus on a broader range of plant feedstocks (Himmel et al., 2007), like switchgrass, miscanthus, or other grasses, which are less vulnerable to pests and climate extremes and can be grown on marginal lands, making them preferred over fertilizers and pesticides. Making use of the capacity to degrade organic matter, the biofuel industry is screening environmental microbes for genes and metabolic pathways (using DSI) that can convert resistant plant chemicals into fermentable sugars. Risks associated with introducing microbes into new ecosystems should be considered when evaluating opportunities.

2.5.2. Magnitudes of sectoral dependencies at the level of nations

Several studies highlight the varying dependence of economic sectors on biodiversity and nature’s contributions to people, including clean water, pest control, pollination, and food and feed supply.

⁸ Details of the analysis are provided in the accompanying data management report: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17239488>

These are essential for industries such as agriculture, fisheries, pharmaceuticals, and tourism (**Table 2.4**). Dependencies vary significantly by region, sector and nature's contributions to people. The contribution of individual nature's contributions to people can make up from 2-8 per cent of a country's GDP, such as with fisheries in Senegal (see **Figure 2.7**) or shark-based tourism in Palau. Individual nature's contributions to people contribute billions to national economies, such as pest control services at \$ 70 million, pollination services for agriculture at \$ 12-34 billion, and habitat provision supporting tourism at \$ 22-39 billion.

Table 2.4. Examples of magnitudes from studies providing evidence at a national level.

Country and source	Sector	NCP	Magnitude	Unit
Italy (Guidetti et al., 2014)	Fisheries	Biomass provisioning	Fisherfolks obtain an 18 times higher catch in MPAs vs outside MPAs	Ratio
Senegal (De Graaf & Garibaldi, 2014), see (Figure 2.7)	Fisheries	Biomass provisioning	The total contribution of fisheries to the GDP is 1.7 per cent, while the post-harvest sector of fisheries, including processing and marketing (value chain), contributes 2.4 per cent to the GDP.	Contribution to nations' GDP in percentage
United States of America (Losey & Vaughan, 2006)	Agriculture	Regulation of organisms detrimental to humans	Dung beetles reduce the habitat for cattle parasites by 19 per cent in the USA. Without these beetles, annual losses due to parasite infections are estimated at \$ 70 million.	\$
Brazil (Giannini et al., 2015)	Agriculture	Pollination services	The total contribution of pollination services to the national agricultural product accounts for ~30 per cent (~ \$ 12 billion).	\$
United States of America (Jordan et al., 2021)	Agriculture	Pollination services	\$ 34 billion in 2012; 20 per cent of United States of America counties produce 80 per cent of total economic value attributable to insect pollinators.	\$
Australia (Cook et al., 2007)	Agriculture	Pollination services	Maintaining a honeybee population free of parasitic infestations (i.e., Varroa mite) represents a benefit of \$4–38.8 million per year for a total of 25 crops.	\$/year
Palau (Vianna et al., 2012)	Arts, entertainment, and recreation	Physical and psychological experiences	The shark diving industry generates \$ 18 million annually, accounting for 8 per cent of the country's GDP.	\$
United States of America (Erin Carver, 2019).	Recreation and tourism	Physical and psychological experiences	Birders in an established birding economy like the USA are estimated to spend ~ \$ 39 billion annually on birding related expenses, generating ~ \$ 16 billion in tax revenue and ~ \$ 96 billion in total industry output.	\$
United States of America (Losey & Vaughan, 2006)	Recreation and tourism	Physical and psychological experiences	Insects are crucial for the diets of small game and birds (important for hunting and birdwatching), with their total value estimated at around \$ 21.8 billion.	\$
Costa Rica (Barbier & Aylward, 1996)	Manufacturing (pharmaceutical and	Medicinal, biochemical	Net private returns of pharmaceutical prospecting in Costa Rica are estimated at \$ 4.8 million.	\$ (1990)

	biotechnology industry)	and genetic resources		
Australia (Australian Bureau of Statistics, 2022)	Electricity, gas steam and air conditioning supply	Water quantity and flow regulation	Electricity and gas supply in Australia in the years 2021-22 used approximately 49,802 Gigalitres (GL) of self-extracted surface water, 50 Gigalitres (GL) of self-extracted groundwater, and 151 GL of distributed water. Total water use, the sum of self-extracted water use, distributed water use, reuse water use, and wastewater collected, was approximately 50,009 GL.	Gigalitres

The contribution of fisheries to African countries' GDP is estimated at \$ 24 billion, equivalent to 1.26 per cent of GDP (De Graaf & Garibaldi, 2014) (Figure 2.7).

Figure 2.7. Contribution to GDP by fishing sub-sector by gross value added (GVA). The size of the pie signifies the overall contribution of the fisheries sector to GDP. The highest contribution is from marine artisanal fishing contributing 1.82

percent of total GDP. Aquaculture contributes the least. Figure borrowed from (De Graaf & Garibaldi, 2014).

National economies differ in their dependence on biodiversity, with non-material benefit highly important for some economies than regulating and material benefits. Using a multi-regional input output (MRIO) tier (i.e., value chain) analysis with Resolved EXIOBASE version 3 (REX3) and ENCORE databases (ENCORE, n.d.), we traced operational and value chain dependencies on nature for Kenya and Brazil. This shows not only which ecosystem services are essential to the economy, but also how those dependencies are embedded in complex, multi-tiered supply chains (**Figure 2.8**). Both economies rely directly on ecosystem services, but Brazil's industries and export-driven sectors depend more on higher-tier links, making it vulnerable to international shocks. Kenya's resource-based economy is highly exposed to natural capital disruptions (in land and water), aggravated by the limited economic diversification. The analysis also highlights tourism's importance in Kenya, where spiritual, artistic and symbolic services and visual amenity services play a key role.

While ENCORE (ENCORE, n.d.) is widely used in dependency assessments for its strengths, any results should be evaluated with its limitations in mind. ENCORE provides the currently most comprehensive dataset on potential dependencies for all economic sectors. It is widely adopted in business practices and recommended by multiple corporate reporting initiatives. It uses qualitative, expert-based scoring for assessing potential dependencies per ISIC sector. However, as is common for business-focused tools, the scores are difficult to verify. The scores do not provide insight in the quantitative magnitude of dependencies on biodiversity and should be compared to the actual availability of resources and context-specific state of biodiversity if the aim is to assess risks. The scores do not consider differences in dependencies on biodiversity between different countries or locations. Overall, the database has not been academically peer-reviewed; 45 per cent of references are scientific literature, 28 per cent are grey literature, 6 per cent are corporate reports, and 21 per cent are websites, some of which are generic public sources or commercial pages; and relies considerably on a small number of sources: 20 sources account for 50 per cent of ecosystem service – ISIC sector combinations.

Figure 2.8. Comparison of ecosystem service dependencies of the national economies of Brazil and Kenya. By using the REX 3 multi-regional input output database combined with the ENCORE database (ENCORE, n.d.). The bars reflect the number of times that an ecosystem service is listed as a “High” or “Very High”

dependency of an economic activity. Note the different scales on the axis for Brazil and Kenya. Details of the analysis are provided in the accompanying data management report (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17239489>).

2.5.3. Dependencies in national financial systems

Several central banks have assessed the economic value underpinned by nature's contributions to people in their respective national financial systems. Overall, between 36 per cent and 98 per cent of portfolios of the central banks with existing assessments are highly or very highly dependent on ecosystem services, depending on the sectoral composition of portfolios and the weights of individual sectors in each portfolio. The top dependencies are for Lithuania (98 per cent), European Union (75 per cent), and Mexico (61 per cent). These studies all rely on the ENCORE database, and some studies also link with the Exiobase (an environmentally extended multiregional input-output database) to assess dependencies embedded in trade (**Table 2.5**)⁹. The largest dependencies are recorded for water-related services (surface water, groundwater, water flow maintenance), climate regulation, flood and storm protection, mass stabilization and erosion control. These dependencies can translate into both physical risks and transition risks (van Toor et al., 2020).

⁹ Details of the analysis are provided in the accompanying data management report: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17239488>

Table 2.5. Summary of central bank studies on business dependencies on nature's contributions to people. Numbers represent available rankings, from 1 (highest, darker) to 5 (lowest, lighter). Note: ENCORE ranks ecosystem services dependencies on a 5-point scale of very-low/low/medium/high/very-high (ENCORE, n.d.); the table includes (very) high dependencies

	Surface water	Climate regulation	Ground-water	Flood and storm protection	Mass stabilization and erosion control	Water flow maintenance	Share highly dependent on ≥1 ecosystem service	Portfolio	ISIC sectors (top dependencies, from highest to lowest)
Kingdom of the Netherlands (van Toor et al., 2020)	1	2	3	4	5		36 per cent	Loans, securities	L H C10, C11 F B
France (Hadji-Lazaro et al., 2024; Svartzman et al., 2021)	1	5	2	4	3		42 per cent	Securities	A01 C10 F36 F37
Brazil (Calice et al., 2021)	1	3	2	4	5		46 per cent	NFC loans	D C10 F G A01
Malaysia (World Bank & Bank Negara Malaysia (BNM), 2022a)	1	2	3	4	5		54 per cent	Commercial loans	L F G A01 C10
United Kingdom	1	4		2	3	5	52 per cent	Loans, securities	D A01 Q C20 A02
Georgia (Nikuradze & Tvalodze, 2023; UNEP-WCMC, 2024)	1	4	2	3	5		46 per cent	Commercial loans	F G L I A01
Mexico (Martinez-Jaramillo et al., 2023)	1	3	2	4		5	61 per cent	NFC loans	A F L G C
European Union (Boldrini et al., 2023)	Not stated						75 per cent	NFC loans	Not Stated
Lithuania (Borges & Laurinaitytė, 2023)	1	5	2	3	4		98 per cent	Commercial loans	Not stated
	Top sectors in terms of dependencies across studies (ISIC section [ISIC Divisions, if noted]): A. Agriculture, forestry and fishing B. Mining and quarrying C. Manufacturing [of food products; of beverages; of chemicals and chemical products] D. Electricity, gas, steam and air conditioning supply E. Water supply; sewerage, waste management and remediation activities F. Construction G. Wholesale and retail trade; repair of motor vehicles and motorcycles H. Transportation and storage I. Accommodation and food service activities [Accommodation] L. Real estate activities Q. Public administration and defence; compulsory social security								

2.5.4. Magnitude of dependencies at the subnational level

Most subnational assessments of sector dependencies provide key insights for business operations. **Table 2.6** summarises selected studies from the literature, covering multiple countries and nature’s contributions to people. These studies mainly focus on the agricultural sector, followed by arts, entertainment and recreation. Dependencies are measured through various metrics including economic value, productivity (volume and employment), quality, and risk. Some studies integrate multiple methods to measure nature’s contributions to people. For example, Tremlett et al. (2021) combine field experiments, stakeholder surveys and economic valuation to quantify pollination dependence. Only few studies incorporate uncertainty analysis, which is crucial for understanding long-term management effects, for instance by providing confidence intervals, using sensitivity analysis, or comparing results across different input data sources (e.g., López-Cubillos et al., 2021)).

Table 2.6. Overview of studies at subnational level of the dependencies of economic activities on nature’s contributions to people, together with the metrics and a summary of the study results and methods used.

A01-03: Agricultural sector			
Nature’s contributions to people*		Metric & frequency*	Examples
Material	Pollination (N = 38)	Economic value N = 25	Summary: Pollination services by bats were estimated at \$ 2,500/ha in pitaya crops by boosting both fruit yield and size, accounting for approximately 40 per cent of the total income for producers in a region of Mexico (Tremlett et al., 2021). Methods: Location-based observations of pollinator exclusion experiments, market pricing and value chain analysis.
		Productivity N = 22	Summary: Wild bee pollination positively impacted the quality and quantity of blueberry production, through an increase in seed set, fruit mass, and fruit set. Not controlling for baseline yields, pollen limitation reduced yields (kg/ha) and associated revenue (\$/ha) by between 1 and 36 per cent per farm in the USA (Nicholson & Ricketts, 2019). Methods: Location-based observations. Pollination supplementation experiments, pollinator observations, and yield estimates.
		Quality N = 9	Summary: In Israel, the addition of bumblebees in Gala-cultivar apple orchards increased the mean number of seeds per fruit by 80 per cent, which also generally reflected a greater fruit size (Sapir et al., 2017). Methods: Location-based observations. Bee colony treatments, pollinator activity observations, and seed and fruit size measurements.
		Risk N = 9	Summary: In Costa Rica, with a complete clearance of habitat important for pollinators, coffee yield could suffer a 23 per cent drop, while preserving forests for pollinators

			<p>could boost average yield by 6 per cent compared to the baseline scenario (López-Cubillos et al., 2021).</p> <p>Methods: Ecological Modelling & Geospatial Mapping. Spatial explicit optimization model using geospatial mapping of forest area important for pollinators combined with coffee land suitability.</p>
Water quantity (N = 16)	Productivity N = 13	<p>Summary: The highest blue and green water requirements of three main grain crops (rice, wheat and corn) in eight regions of China (PRC) for rice, wheat and corn, were found in South-central China (2.45 m³/kg), South-Central China (2.16 m³/kg) and Northwest China (1.22 m³/kg), respectively (Y. B. Wang et al., 2014).</p> <p>Methods: Biophysical approaches. water foot printing, effective precipitation and the actual water use method (volume by field water consumption and irrigated water loss)</p>	
	Risk N = 8	<p>Summary: Six different cropping patterns and water supply scenarios are generated to predict the effects of cropping adjustments on groundwater sustainability of the North China Plain. Irrigation requirements need to be limited to 187 mm/a to sustain current groundwater levels; 34 per cent of the land should be left fallow every year or all cropland should be left fallow every 3 years to sustain current agricultural practices, groundwater sustainability, food supply, water use efficiency, and soil fertility recovery (Ren et al., 2021) .</p> <p>Methods: Ecological Modelling & Geospatial Mapping. Decision Support for Agro-technology Transfer (DSSAT) crop- and regression model; it simulates crop growth and agricultural water use, using weather, soil, crop cultivar and management practises as inputs.</p>	
Food and feed (N = 1)	Productivity N = 1	<p>Summary: Lamb and wool production in Argentina appropriate 11 per cent of total Net Primary Productivity (NPP), highlighting its dependence on ecosystem productivity. Human Appropriation of Net Primary Productivity (HANPP) is lower in ecotones and wetlands but higher in intensively managed northwest and central regions. Its negative correlation with plant biodiversity and carbon balance suggests a trade-off between provisioning services and ecosystem health (Peri et al., 2022).</p> <p>Methods: Ecological Modelling & Geospatial Mapping. HANPP; simple linear regression.</p>	
Regulation of organisms detrimental to humans (N=2)	Productivity N = 2	<p>Summary: Over multiple spatial scales, landscape-level crop diversification increased biological control of aphids in winter wheat fields in Germany. In fields with high landscape-level crop diversity, biological control was 8 to 33 per cent higher than in fields with low landscape-level crop diversity, with main effects observed on scales less than 500 metres (Redlich et al., 2018).</p>	

			Methods: natural enemy exclusion experiment.
	Medicinal, biochemical and genetic resources (N=1)	Economic value N = 1	Summary: Basmati rice landraces outperformed modern varieties like Sabitri and China-4 in gross and net margins, with a 17 per cent net marketing margin compared to Sabitri's 10 per cent in Nepal. While coarse-grained landraces like Mutmur thrive in marginal conditions, they fetch lower prices, but households growing both types had 3.3 extra months of rice self-sufficiency (Gauchan et al., 2005). Methods: Participatory market systems analysis and baseline survey of farm and household characteristics, perceptions of traits, and access to resources (primarily qualitative).
	Material and assistance (N=1)	Productivity N = 1	Summary: Landscape composition (land cover in 20km radius around main cities of municipalities) accounted for 25, 77 and 64 per cent of the total employment in the agriculture subsector and 33, 67 and 23 per cent of employment in the animal production and forestry subsector for Coastal Patagonia, the main irrigated valley (Valley of Rio Negro), and Andean Patagonia, respectively, in Argentina (Laterra et al., 2021). Methods: Generalised additive models and multiple regression analysis.
R90-93: Arts, entertainment, and recreation			
Non-Material	Physical and psychological experiences (N=1)	Quality N = 1	Summary: In the Libo Carst in South China, 26 landscapes were identified as aesthetic value carriers and ranked by experts based on aesthetic value scores, complemented with existence values (e.g., intrinsic value of its characteristics such as geological unique features) and potential value (e.g., the cultural aspects of a site) (Xiong et al., 2023). Methods: evaluation scores built from combination of online text big data analysis, expert landscape beauty evaluation, and ArcGIS spatial analysis
	Habitat creation and maintenance (N=2)	Productivity N = 1	Summary: Landscape composition (land cover in 20km radius around main cities of municipalities) explained 34, 50 and 78 per cent of variation in employment in tourism across Coastal Patagonia, irrigated valley (Valley of Rio Negro), and Andean Patagonia respectively. The number of employments explained by landscape composition per each employment in the tourism subsector was 1.29, 1.9 and 2.96 for Coastal Patagonia, the main irrigated valley (Valley of Rio Negro), and Andean Patagonia respectively (Laterra et al., 2021). Methods: Generalised additive models and multiple regression analysis.

		Quality and economic value N = 1	Summary: Tourists varied in their cognition of four rare species (Giant Panda, Golden Monkey, Crested Ibis, and Takin) in protected areas of the Qinling region in China. Tourists are willing to pay 26 per cent more on an annual basis above the entrance ticket for the Giant Panda and Golden Monkey (36 RMB), and less for the Crested Ibis and Takin (26 RMB) ((Yang et al., 2022)). Methods: Contingent valuation method; perception survey.
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2.5.5. Magnitude of business risks from dependencies

Multiple studies assess macro-level risks from biodiversity loss, showing variation across sectors and countries under different scenarios. These what-if scenarios vary in scope, with more recent studies adding new components and moving from physical risks to more systemic risks (e.g., Johnson et al., 2021), however, none of the studies fully quantifies the systemic risks of biodiversity’s loss.

Table 2.7. summarizes findings linking biodiversity loss to economic value declines using scenario-based models. Recent studies include all ecosystem services in ENCORE (Ranger et al., 2023, 2024), while earlier research focuses on select nature’s contributions to people or undifferentiating impacts. Loss of biodiversity poses risks to businesses across all scales with some country having better adaptation capability than others. For example, pollination loss could reduce global GDP by 1 to 3 per cent, depending on the model. Some nations, like the Netherlands, may increase agricultural output substituting production in countries with higher reliance on pollination (Prodani et al., 2023), but lower-income countries would struggle to reduce poverty when pollination, timber and fishery services are lost (Johnson et al., 2021).

Deterioration of other biodiversity also poses risks. Losing disease control services due to antimicrobial resistance could reduce GDP of the United Kingdom by 12 per cent loss, surpassing COVID-19 losses (Ranger et al., 2024). Loss of nature’s contributions to people could destabilise finances by increasing non-performing loans (up to 2.75x increase in financial losses in the European Union, 4x in some countries, and by 9 percentage points in Brazil) (Calice et al., 2021).

Table 2.7. Summary of results from studies on risks to the economy from loss of nature’s contributions to people

Nature’s contributions to people	Core finding
Fisheries	High seas (Areas beyond national jurisdiction) fisheries will not be economically viable under future climate change without measures to enhance the sustainability of fisheries, such as Marine Protected Areas (Cheung et al., 2019) ¹⁰ .
	With sound management reforms, global fisheries can yield value of \$ 53 billion annually (Cheung et al., 2019)
Pollination	Decline: Global short-run losses: \$ 127 – 152 billion (2004 price levels); (Bauer & Sue Wing, 2016)
	Decline: Global long-run losses: \$ 574 – 1,318 billion (2017 price levels) (Lippert et al., 2021)
	Decline: -1 per cent global GDP (Ranger et al., 2023)
	Collapse: Netherlands: +38 per cent agricultural prices, +23 per cent agricultural output, limited effect on GDP (Prodani et al., 2023)
Timber + Fisheries + Pollination	Partial collapse: -2.3 per cent GDP, -10 per cent for poorest countries (Johnson et al., 2021)
	Brazil: +9 per cent points rise in non-performing loans (Calice et al., 2021), based on Johnson et al. (2021)
Water quantity and quality	Global: -7-9 per cent GDP (Ranger et al., 2023)
Pest and disease control	United Kingdom: -12 per cent GDP (antimicrobial resistance scenario) (Ranger et al., 2024)
All ecosystem services in scope	European Union: +2.5 to 2.75 times financial losses. Up to 4 times losses for Germany, Lithuania (Boldrini et al., 2023)
	Malaysia: 16-44 per cent of financial portfolio affected under most significant ecosystem services reduction scenarios (World Bank & Bank Negara Malaysia (BNM), 2022b)
	United Kingdom: -6 per cent GDP (Ranger et al., 2024)
	Global: Effects of decline in all ENCORE ecosystem services has been assessed in Ranger et al. (2024) and (2023)

Despite widespread statements about biodiversity dependencies underpinning GDP, firm-level scientific evidence linking biodiversity and company performance is scarce (Karolyi & Tobin-de la Puente, 2023). Few academic studies examine nature-related dependencies in company performance,

¹⁰ Note that while this study focuses on Marine Protected Areas in particular, it does not explore the full range of potential policy options and does not aim to prescribe specific policies for fisheries management.

while most focus on impacts (Akey & Appel, 2021; Flammer et al., 2023; Garel et al., 2023; Hsu et al., 2023; Xin et al., 2023).

Businesses anticipate biodiversity risks using qualitative survey data (Giglio et al., 2023, Wagner, 2023), and quantitative financial market data ((Hoepner et al., 2023), (Giglio et al., 2023), (Coqueret & Giroux, 2023), but are unprepared to manage them. A global survey of 48 financial businesses managing \$ 33 trillion in assets found only 25 per cent identified nature-related risks, with 68 per cent still assessing them. Additionally, 36 per cent introduced nature-related risk management only in the last 2 years. Key barriers include availability of data, reliable models, and scenarios (Paisley & Nelson, 2024).

Self-reported business data confirms this gap. The 2024 World Benchmarking Alliance Nature Benchmark reviewed 816 businesses across 21 sectors, finding just 6 businesses in the sample (0.7 per cent of total) assessed dependencies. A review of Fortune 500 disclosures of 100 businesses found similar results (Trim & Jones, 2025). In 2018, an estimated 1759 listed businesses with biodiversity policies (29 per cent of the top 85 per cent listed businesses by value) represented \$51.1 trillion in total enterprise value (Carvalho et al., 2023a). Water-risk disclosure is more established: of 2,934 businesses disclosing to CDP Water in 2021 (a quarter of global market cap), 41 per cent reported water stress/scarcity risks, 27 per cent flood regulation, 17 per cent water flow maintenance, 8 per cent water quality, and 7 per cent disaster risk reduction (CDP, 2021).

2.6. Implications for society

This section outlines the relevance of the academic methods from **Sections 2.3** and **2.4** in guiding societal actors toward sustainable business-biodiversity interactions. While sustainable action also requires stakeholder engagement, collaborative frameworks (L. H. Huang et al., 2024), and analyses of roles and relationships of governments, businesses, consumers, and civil society (Carvalho et al., 2023b; Reale et al., 2019), this section focuses on the use dependency assessment methods.

2.6.1. Implications for government and policymakers

Integrating biodiversity into economic reporting enables policymakers to guide corporate activities towards sustainability (Booth et al., 2024), develop evidence-based and targeted regulations, design economic incentives, and enhance corporate transparency and accountability (Ingram et al., 2024; Mohr & Thissen, 2022). National natural capital accounting frameworks, combining biophysical and monetary valuation methods, help quantify business dependencies on natural resources (Grunewald et al., 2024). While over 90 nations have piloted natural capital accounting initiatives, and specifically the System of Environmental-Economic Accounting Ecosystem Accounting - Ecosystem Accounting (SEEA-EA) framework (United Nations Statistics Division, 2023), most remain in early stages.

Global environmental-economic models inform national strategies for global commitments under the Convention on Biological Diversity (including mainstreaming of biodiversity in economic sectors) and the Paris Agreement, identifying areas where ecosystem restoration can mitigate risks. More detailed valuation methods and behavioural experiments help identify distributive impacts and design public policy instruments that incentivise sustainable behaviour by businesses or households. Integrated methods can help develop economic strategies that consider the plural values in society. To ensure business accountability, biophysical methods like remote sensing or field-based measurements are crucial for monitoring natural capital stocks and flows, while corporate document analysis aid transparency but is insufficient for evaluating compliance. Biophysical models are also used to identify changes in critically endangered species and habitats, motivating further public investment into conservation and restoration (Retser et al., 2020) seed banks, genetic information, and so on.

2.6.2. Implications for businesses and financial institutions

Businesses can integrate biodiversity into their models and implement sustainable biodiversity strategies by assessing nature-related dependencies, impacts, and risks (Jones & Wynn, 2024). Effective evaluation requires combining ecological and financial datasets (Mohr & Thissen, 2022) to identify exposure, hazard, vulnerability, and opportunities to mitigate risks through reducing impacts or investing in restoration, collaborating with communities, or consumer engagement. However, current risk assessment methods have notable limitations and constraints (Smith et al. 2024) (Smith et al., 2024).

Financial institutions increasingly acknowledge nature-related risks and are implementing disclosures for risk management and regulatory compliance (Barning et al., 2024). Biophysical methods help materiality screens of dependency risks based on operational, legal, financial, and reputational criteria (Mohr & Thissen, 2022). While major sectors (agriculture, forestry, extractives, etc.) have adopted biophysical approaches (Addison & Bull, 2018; WEF, 2020b), they mostly assess impacts rather than dependencies. Businesses use the ENCORE database (see **Table 2.4**) for risk screening, though it lacks the capacity to quantify dependency risks. The Finance Sector Deforestation Action initiative, representing \$8.9 trillion in assets, assessed deforestation risks, focusing on identifying high-risk regions, sectors, and priority forest-risk commodities to understand their overall risk profile, including

their physical risk, financial risk and transition risk. They set targets to eliminate deforestation risks from agricultural commodity investments and lending by 2025, with full phase-out by 2030 (Institutional Investors Group on Climate Change (IIGCC), 2024)

Corporate adoption of nature-related financial risk assessments (TNFD, 2023b) and natural capital assessments (Natural Capital Coalition, 2016; WEF, 2020b) is growing, with businesses using monetary valuation to quantify ecosystem value and anticipate liabilities tied to natural resource depletion. However, these applications have so far assessed impact values, as seen in the Kering, (2018) Environmental Profit & Loss (EP&L) accounts. Some marketing reports use stated preference methods to evaluate demand for products with eco-labels or sustainable certifications, highlighting markets where sustainable levels of use (dependencies) can be profitable (Bar Am et al., 2023; PricewaterhouseCoopers (PwC), 2024) Key knowledge gaps remain in how business and finance can apply non-market valuation to justify investment in natural capital and how to adapt their internal decision-making criteria (e.g., minimum return-on-investment, investment size, or payback period requirements). If conditions changed such that non-marketed values would be valued by the market, and paid for by consumers or otherwise, this could render sustainable practices (more) profitable.

Socio-cultural valuation is emerging as businesses seek support of communities for a licence to operate. Global frameworks, such as the Kunming-Montreal Global Biodiversity Framework, emphasise rights-based approaches (Convention on Biological Diversity (CBD), 2022). Industries such as mining, forestry, and bioprospecting are beginning to integrate Indigenous and local knowledge into their corporate social responsibility and Free, Prior and Informed Consent compliance (Cariño & Colchester, 2010) (See **Section 2.7**).

Integrated approaches are increasingly recognised in corporate reporting (TNFD, 2023b). For example, Dow Chemical Company partnered with The Nature Conservancy to address future water risks in Texas, using natural capital valuation and multi-criteria analysis to identify cost-effective, nature-based solutions (Reddy et al., 2015). Despite considerable technical, legal and political hurdles, the assessment demonstrated public benefits that opened opportunities for multi-stakeholder collaboration.

2.6.3. Implications for civil society organizations

Multiple methods support civil society and non-governmental organizations promote sustainable business practices. Conservation-oriented non-governmental organizations use biodiversity metrics to track changes in ecosystem health and identify areas at risk. Such assessments help recognize critical tipping points in ecosystems, guiding them in prioritizing conservation efforts (IPBES, 2019d; World Wide Fund for Nature (WWF), 2024).

Biodiversity assessments can highlight overlaps between critical ecosystems and development zones, providing civil society organizations with scientific evidence to advocate for nature-inclusive policies. For example, global scenario analyses show where conserving 30 per cent of the planet by 2030 could most benefit climate, jobs, and health (McKinsey & Company, 2020). In China, ecological footprint studies reveal that footprints tripled from 1978 to 2013, while ecological carrying capacity grew only slightly, leading to greater ecological insecurity (Z. Wang et al., 2018).

Participatory assessment strengthens evaluations by incorporating civil society organization and community input. Local community engagement in Colombia shaped strategies aligning cultural heritage with biodiversity goals (Echeverri et al., 2025). In China's Yongding River Corridor, modelling and community surveys identified green infrastructure solutions (Wong et al., 2018). In Portugal, stakeholder engagement was used to articulate diverse values and defined sustainable interventions for tourism and recreation dependent areas (Lopes & Videira, 2016).

By quantifying economic benefits of nature's contributions to people, civil society organizations can support Payments for Ecological Services schemes, incentivising biodiversity-friendly practices (Nelson et al., 2009; Neugarten et al., 2018). Stated preference studies show that tourists are willing to pay premiums for sustainably managed coral reef areas, creating business opportunities for conservation NGOs in collaboration with tourism and recreation businesses.

2.6.4. Implications for consumers

Consumer representatives can use various methods to inform governments and businesses about consumer preferences for sustainable products and ethical strategies to influence consumer behaviour. Valuation methods assessing economic and socio-cultural values help raise awareness of the importance of biodiversity and origin of the products and drive behavioural change (BCG, 2021), strengthening consumer-nature connections. For example, stated preference methods gauge consumer willingness to pay for improved water service quality (Kim et al., 2021), biodiversity conservation in tourism (Gross et al., 2023; Surendran & Sekar, 2010; P.-W. Wang & Jia, 2012), forests' cultural ecosystem services (Acharya et al., 2021; W.-J. Chen et al., 2022), and sustainable supermarket products (Gatti et al., 2022; Tokuoka et al., 2024). These studies show how understanding biodiversity dependencies enables consumers to make greener choices and support eco-friendly businesses.

2.7. Implications of business dependencies on biodiversity for Indigenous Peoples and local communities

Business dependencies intersect with rights over lands, territories, waters, resources of IPLCs, as well as their Indigenous and local knowledge, which supports their cultural values, identity and livelihoods. This section explores the interrelationships between IPLCs and biodiversity, the role of Indigenous and local knowledge in how businesses assess their dependencies on biodiversity, and IPLCs' businesses.

2.7.1. Interrelationships between Indigenous Peoples and local communities with biodiversity

Increasing environmental risks as well as regulatory and disclosure frameworks, has prompted businesses to consider how biodiversity supports businesses at an operational level and throughout the value chain (Dasgupta, 2021). However, this understanding is largely framed through an instrumental logic, where biodiversity is valued for its contributions to people such as pollination, water purification, climate regulation, or supply of raw materials. The concept of 'business dependencies' on biodiversity sometimes suggests a two-dimensional relationship, the conversion of biodiversity to manufactured and financial capital (Gómez-Baggethun) and the impacts of businesses on biodiversity. More recently, there has been a push to consider the multidimensional relationship between the broader nature and humans including businesses. However, IPLCs view biodiversity from a relational perspective, through an interconnected bond described as a 'mutual interrelationship' with nature (IPBES et al., 2023). The relationship with nature is multidimensional and shaped by principles of care, obligation, and interdependence, where both humans and nature have responsibilities toward each other (Díaz et al., 2018; Irvine et al., 2019) This symbiotic worldview encourages IPLCs to safeguard biodiversity while deriving sustenance, reflecting a deeply spiritual connection and a philosophy of reciprocity (Cloud & Redvers, 2023; Mazzocchi, 2020). This reflects contrasting views between relational worldviews of a mutual interrelationship with nature and instrumental worldviews that promote the exploitation and degradation of nature (IPBES, 2024).

This epistemic divergence presents a growing challenge for businesses seeking to assess and manage their nature-related dependencies. Standard corporate approaches to biodiversity are characterized by environmental accounting, risk disclosure, and ecosystem service valuation, which overlooks the ontological and ethical dimensions of biodiversity as understood by IPLCs (Tadaki et al., 2017; Turnhout et al., 2013). When nature is framed solely by its instrumental values as natural capital to be measured and managed, businesses may overlook how their dependencies on biodiversity may conflict with or undermine the values, rights, and relationships that IPLCs have with biodiversity. This divergence contrasts with corporate efforts to assess their nature-related dependencies, leading to blind spots in risk assessments, stakeholder engagement, and the design of sustainability strategies. Without grappling with these plural ways of knowing and relating to biodiversity, businesses risk reinforcing epistemic and procedural injustices when they measure and address their dependencies on biodiversity. Moving beyond instrumental valuation and embracing more pluralistic, inclusive approaches to biodiversity involves recognizing the rights and self-determination of IPLCs, creating spaces for equitable knowledge co-production, and embedding relational values into corporate governance systems (IPBES et al., 2022; Pascual et al., 2023).

The Organisation for Economic Cooperation and Development (OECD) Guidelines for Multinational Enterprises (OECD MNE Guidelines) and the International Finance Corporation (IFC) Performance Standards on Environmental and Social Sustainability (IFC Performance Standards) are widely viewed as important international standards for guiding responsible transnational business conduct

(Seck, 2016). Yet, the rights of Indigenous Peoples to free, prior and informed consent (FPIC) are not always adequately recognised and sometimes misinterpreted. Moreover, there is a need for national and local standards that recognises the rights of IPLCs. Businesses should engage IPLCs and secure the agreement of local communities to establish operations at a site or make significant changes to existing operations to correct wrongdoing and meet communities' expectations.

2.7.2. Role of Indigenous and local knowledge in how businesses assess their dependencies on biodiversity

Indigenous and local knowledge encompasses governance systems, customary laws, and ecological knowledge including food, medicine, and ecosystem management (Sahoo et al., 2022). Indigenous and local knowledge develops from generations of observation and interaction with the natural world, shaping Indigenous identities and responsibilities toward the environment (Jessen et al., 2022; Pierotti & Wildcat, 2000). This knowledge includes nuanced understandings of species behaviour, ecological variability, and socio-environmental feedback, often extending beyond the temporal and spatial resolution of conventional ecological monitoring. For instance, the Yolngu people in Australia have detailed knowledge of seasonal cycles to manage water and food resources (Prober et al., 2011). IPLCs possess expertise in weather forecasting, managing forests, and preserving water sources (Abas et al., 2022). Indigenous and local knowledge can therefore play a big role in biophysical quantification or socio-cultural and economic valuation assessments of business dependencies on biodiversity.

Indigenous and local knowledge offers valuable insights for ecosystem management (Mistry et al., 2016; Reyes-García et al., 2016; Tengö et al., 2017). Indigenous-managed lands often experience lower rates of biodiversity loss and lands located within tropical protected areas often maintain high levels of forest integrity (Dawson et al., 2021; IPBES, 2022; Sze et al., 2024). This knowledge is important in business response to assess and minimize risk to biodiversity along the value chain. Efforts to bridge Indigenous and local knowledge with scientific knowledge enhances conservation practices, such as in northern Australia where traditional knowledge has been integrated into local watershed management (Robinson et al., 2016). Under the Convention on Biological Diversity, Indigenous and local knowledge has been applied in natural resource management, integrated into conservation planning, and implemented in sustainable use initiatives (Parks & Tsioumani, 2023).

While emerging nature-related standards and frameworks aim to assess and disclose dependencies, they remain largely grounded in biophysical and economic metrics. This can result in narrow assessments that fail to capture the full complexity of human–nature relationships, particularly in landscapes managed or inhabited by IPLCs. Indigenous and local knowledge can inform ecological models, improve temporal sensitivity to environmental shifts, and inform culturally relevant indicators of ecosystem health (Berkes, 2018; Tengö et al., 2014). Participatory mapping and monitoring to assess biodiversity dependencies include participatory mapping, community-led monitoring, rights-based approaches, oral histories, and seasonal indicators (Robinson et al., 2016; Tengö et al., 2021). Collaboration and partnerships between businesses and IPLCs can document, preserve and leverage valuable knowledge and resources to build resilience across sectors through comprehensive risk assessments, co-designed monitoring systems, and benefit-sharing mechanisms.

2.7.3. Indigenous Peoples and local communities' businesses

Indigenous businesses often operate business models with generational business strategies, sharing of resources amongst communities and as stewards of biodiversity. For example, in northern Canada, the Inuvialuit operate sustainable fisheries that support local communities and protect Arctic char populations (Tallman et al., 2019). Indigenous businesses create community benefits, as they seek to preserve their culture and rights to self-determination (Peredo & Anderson, 2006; Dana, 2015).

Therefore, Indigenous businesses may use Indigenous methods with indicators that could include social aspects such as cultural events or number of youths or elders supported. In New Zealand, Maori businesses emphasise benefits for the entire community rather than individual profit (Mrabure, 2019). Since benefits are communal, in many instances, accountability is also communal and there are continuous risk assessments to the community. Traditional practices are often associated with sustainable activities through IPLCs' attachment to their ancestral lands and social cooperation (Peredo & Anderson, 2006). Many Indigenous businesses therefore have a social focus (**Table 2.8**, see **Chapter 5** for more information). However, some business sectors such as agriculture, forestry, mining, and energy depend on biodiversity for direct physical inputs, thereby competing for resources with IPLCs.

Businesses' dependencies on biodiversity can conflict with Indigenous Peoples rights, relationships, and their interrelationships with biodiversity. Industrial development expansion threatens 60 per cent of Indigenous lands globally and one-quarter of Indigenous territories are under high pressure for resource exploitation (Kennedy et al., 2023). Demand for minerals vital to the energy transition has escalated these risks, with mining projects frequently overlapping Indigenous territories (Owen, Kemp, Harris, et al., 2022; Owen, Kemp, Lechner, et al., 2022). For example, 80 per cent of lithium projects are located on Indigenous lands, and water scarcity in these regions compounds the risks of pollution (International Renewable Energy Agency (IRENA) & International Labour Organization (ILO), 2024; Lèbre et al., 2020). These activities may restrict IPLCs' access to sacred sites, land and water, or disrupt their traditional land management practices that have evolved over generations (see **Chapter 3** for more information).

Climate change further exacerbates challenges for IPLCs, disrupting traditional food systems, agriculture, and cultural values (Jarillo & Crivelli, 2024; Reyes-García et al., 2023). Island communities are some of the most vulnerable to climate change; rising sea levels threatens water supplies, food systems from land and sea, respiratory illnesses and mental health effects (Keener et al., 2021) These impacts disrupt cultural practices and threaten the economic, social, and spiritual well-being of IPLCs (Ksenofontov & Petrov, 2024; Pearson et al., 2023; Yletyinen et al., 2022).

Table 2.8. Indigenous Peoples and local communities’ businesses with an emphasis on mutual interrelationships with biodiversity.

Country	IPLCs’ business description	Ecological focus	Social focus
Colombia	Tree nursery businesses owned by IPLCs support reforestation, recover rare plant species, and preserve biodiversity (IPBES et al., 2023).	Seed preservation businesses have developed to safeguard genetic resources that are increasingly valuable due to scarcity.	Plant species can be exchanged or sold for money. Access to rare plant species that have important cultural elements supports IPLCs in re-discovering their traditional foods and origins.
Indonesia	Planet Indonesia, a nonprofit organization, assists IPLCs in West Kalimantan in community-led governance of ecosystems through village partnerships (Planet Indonesia, 2024).	One of the organization’s partnerships in Gunung Nyiut led to improved conservation outcomes and reduced deforestation rates.	Using a rights-based approach, their efforts focus on securing communities’ formal legal tenure and rights over lands and resources, as well as financial inclusion and regenerative livelihoods from small-scale fisheries, agriculture, and ecotourism.
Kenya	The Samburu community collaborates with the Sarara Foundation on conservation and ecotourism within Namunyak Conservancy. Combines pastoral farming, ecotourism, and wildlife conservation. Revenue generated from tourism, lodging, and conservation fees funds ecosystem protection, water development, education, and healthcare for the community (Sarara / The Sarara Foundation, n.d.)	This business has contributed to the survival of endangered species like the Grévy’s zebra and the Reticulated giraffe, as well other species such as zebras, hyenas, kudus, lions and leopards.	Empowerment of female entrepreneurs who sell goat milk to the Reteti Elephant Sanctuary, fostering local economic opportunities. A recognition of Indigenous communities’ land rights through obtaining title deeds for the Sarara and Sapashe communities.

2.8. Trade-offs and synergies in dependencies

Businesses that rely on biodiversity and nature’s contributions to people often face complex decisions that involve balancing trade-offs and fostering synergies between economic goals and social and environmental sustainability (see also **Chapters 3 and 6**). These trade-offs and synergies are a feature of the conditions of the system within which business operates. Recognizing these dynamics is crucial to identify suitable actions.

Synergies and trade-offs involve questions around the fair allocation of scarce resources (related to equitable development as a societal goal). Trade-offs occur when a decision or action to enhance or maximize one aspect either for economic growth may decrease or compromise biodiversity and nature’s contributions to people or impact IPLCs and other communities. For businesses, this often involves balancing short-term economic gains with long-term sustainability, including risks of biodiversity loss and impacts on the business itself, nature, and external stakeholders (Howe et al., 2014). Synergies refer to interactions where multiple benefits are derived simultaneously from biodiversity and nature’s contributions to people; these can result from business actions to restore ecosystems (Brancalion et al., 2022; Mohr & Metcalf, 2018). Synergies can arise because of dependencies in “production spheres”, e.g., when the nature’s contributions to people are bundled (Spake et al., 2017) or interdependent such as in the water-energy-food-biodiversity nexus (Doelman et al., 2022). Joint investment in multifunctional landscapes (Medina-Roldán et al., 2024), or in non-consumptive use of public goods may also create business synergies. Synergies can also arise because of shared objectives, e.g., shared (interdependent) needs, dependencies or objectives of different stakeholders, for example in case of social enterprises, or shared resources (Katic et al., 2023). **Table 2.9** provides a typology of trade-offs and their synergy equivalents.

Table 2.9. Typology of trade-offs and synergies among businesses, society, and biodiversity.

Trade-offs within the business	Synergies within the business
The risk of biodiversity loss that affects the business itself, such as removing natural habitat essential for pollination services (e.g., López-Cubillos et al., 2021).	The opportunities for improving biodiversity or nature’s contributions to people to generate profitability for the business, such as the restoration of natural habitat that improves pollinators’ abundance and the services they provide, which leads to an increase in yields or quality (e.g., López-Cubillos et al., 2023).
Trade-offs with other businesses	Synergies with other businesses
Trade-offs among sectors that occur when other businesses demand nature’s contributions to people located in the same landscape. Rival nature’s contributions to people occur when one user reduces the availability of such services for other users (Metzger et al., 2021).	Synergies that occur when multiple businesses benefit from an improvement in nature’s contributions to people within the same landscape or production process. For instance, within the same value chain, or in case of non-consumptive use, such as better air quality.
Trade-offs between increasing business profitability with civil society, and IPLCs	Synergies between increasing business profitability with civil society, and IPLCs
Trade-offs that occur when businesses overexploit natural resources that are important for the civil society. Examples include using water resources for agricultural commodities through restricting	Business profitability and dependency should also generate positive impacts on civil society and IPLCs

access for IPLCs (e.g., (Larsimont, 2022) or the opening of international fishing markets that generate profits (to men) but displace women (Porter et al., 2008)	by supporting their reliance on biodiversity and nature’s contributions to people.
Trade-offs between increasing business profitability with biodiversity and nature	Synergies between increasing business profitability with biodiversity and nature
Trade-offs with climate mitigation and biodiversity (e.g., Grass et al., 2020), biosecurity risks related to trade and land competition between business/economic use and the environment.	Creating positive effects on biodiversity

Accounting for the different types of trade-offs and synergies is essential for understanding and managing risk to business, where financial performance and broader environmental and social impacts are integrated into corporate decision-making. By recognizing and quantifying these trade-offs, businesses can better align their operations with sustainability goals and enhance their resilience to environmental and social risks. Understanding shared objectives or needs requires assessment to consider the diverse values and worldviews of all actors involved (IPBES, 2022). These can be mapped against different business objectives to identify areas of synergies and interdependencies.

Synergies in dependencies suggest that investing in nature’s contributions to people can benefit multiple businesses and societal actors simultaneously. This creates opportunities for businesses to collaborate on sustainable management, secure supply chains, reduce risk and improve business operations (Ya He & Cranston, 2014), and at the same time support dependencies of other non-business actors. Partnerships can foster collective agreements to manage dependencies equitably, benefiting non-business actors. For instance, restoration can provide direct benefits and positive return on investment to farmers and thereby create a business case for purely private investment (López-Cubillos et al., 2023), but this is not the case everywhere; for example, in California, managing natural habitats for pollinators created no net private benefits to individual landowners, but neighbouring landowners benefited from the services provided by mobile pollinators (Lonsdorf et al., 2020). In such cases, payment for ecosystem services schemes can be a viable option (Lonsdorf et al., 2020), if needed combined with carbon payments (d’Albertas et al., 2024). Increasingly businesses, including social enterprises, adopt objectives beyond profit maximization related to social and environmental goals, including issues of equity and justice (Green et al., 2017).

Multiple methods can be used to identify synergies and trade-offs (see **Table 2.10**). Studies at larger spatial scales often use production possibility frontier analysis, and tend to identify synergetic opportunities (Damania et al., 2023) {2.6.2}. Such studies often focus aggregate indicators of resource efficiency and GDP or economic output but ignore distributional effects and wider well-being impacts. More detailed studies on the impacts on individual actors of interventions often find trade-offs, as they are more likely to consider distributional impacts across actors as well as non-monetary impacts (Schaafsma et al., 2021; Schreckenberget al., 2018). For example, shifting to more efficient agriculture through technological innovation may well improve resource efficiency and agricultural revenues, but is unlikely to benefit resource-poor smallholder farmers who may be outcompeted. Marine protected areas may benefit the tourism industry because divers often prefer areas with higher fish density and biomass (Morse et al., 2024), however, excluding local fishermen can lead to food insecurity and displacement (Kamat, 2014). Assessing power imbalances in supply chains or across sectors and spatial scales can help to understand why trade-offs occur or where opportunities for synergies are missed (Martín-López et al., 2019).

However, very few examples of studies demonstrate how individual businesses can create positive societal impacts in how they manage their dependencies on nature’s contributions to people, let alone including compound climate change effects. One example is a study on an international brewery, which examined the extent to which agronomic advice given by corporate farm extension workers would help smallholders (suppliers) to increase income, improve resource efficiency (water, fertiliser, energy) and reduce greenhouse gas emissions, and at the same time secure barley production for the beer company (Bowe & Der Horst, 2015). It is important to note that the same practice can have different outcomes across different geographies. For example, some businesses, which, along with agronomic advice, aim to enhance social and environmental sustainability in farming practices by planting trees (Bianco, 2020). Their producers in Colombia reported positive outcomes from such verification, including increased prices and improved market access and technical support (Rubio-Jovel, 2024). Conversely, producers in Costa Rica noted that the verification favoured only a few producers and hurt cooperatives, despite the program’s positive effects on water conservation (Rubio-Jovel et al., 2024).

Table 2.10. Examples of trade-offs and synergies with different methodological approaches

Trade-off / synergy type	Summary	Sectors	Methods	Nature’s contributions to people	References
Trade-offs within the business	Forest industries, construction and publishing rely on sustained supplies of timber and wood fibre, but can alter forest structure	Forestry/ construction	(Bio)-physical and ecological	Timber	Kallesoe et al. (2012) and Lahntinen et al. (2016)
Trade-offs with other businesses	Fishing unsustainably may negatively impact tourism and angling recreational activities.	Fisheries, Mining and Recreation	Life cycle assessment	Water services, Food production and Cultural services	Blanco et al. (2018)
Trade-offs with civil society and IPLCs	Water pollution caused by eucalyptus plantations in Ecuador resulted in the death of livestock of smallholders.	Industrial tree plantation, smallholder farmers	Participatory and socio-cultural methods + Monetary valuation	Water services	Gerber et al. (2009)

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Trade-offs with nature's contributions to people	Irrigating crops (e.g., rice and corn) in the USA can increase profits but also increase agricultural runoff and degrade surface water quality.	Soybean, corn, rice, wheat, and cotton sectors.	Monetary valuation and efficiency frontiers	Food production and Water services	Kovacs et al. (2017)
Synergies within the business	Conserving and restoring forest patches near coffee farms in Costa Rica can enhance populations of pest-controlling birds and pollinating wild bees, increasing yields and farmers' profitability.	Agriculture (coffee)	(a) Ecological and (b) efficiency frontier analysis	Pollination and pest control services	(a) Karp et al. (2013), (b) López-Cubillos et al. (2023)
Synergies with other businesses	Managing forest for timber production, yield water used for hydropower in Sierra Nevada	Timber and Energy	Economic valuation	Water supply	Guo et al. (2023)
Synergies with Civil Society, and Indigenous Peoples and local communities	Ecotourism enhances the diversification of household income, by creating employment, boosting small businesses and improve social welfare in six southern African countries	Tourism, agriculture and small businesses	Socio-Cultural Valuation Methods	Tourism and cultural heritage	Snyman (2014)

Synergies with biodiversity and climate change	Forest conservation in the Brazilian amazon improves biodiversity, enhances carbon storage and maximises açai palm pollination services	Agriculture, Forestry, carbon storage	Biophysical spatial modelling and Cost benefit analysis	Carbon mitigation; soil erosion control; habitat creation and maintenance	Campbell et al. (2023)
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2.9. Closing and knowledge gaps

The review in this chapter demonstrates that while the existence of nature-related business dependencies and risks is well established, evidence for quantified dependencies for individual business’ operations and value chains is scarce. Nonetheless, the evidence is sufficiently robust for a call for individual business action despite remaining uncertainties (Retsa et al., 2020).

Studies on dependency from our review showed a very skewed distribution with most studies in Americas, Europe and Asia. African and Oceania studies are lacking (see **Figure 2.9**).

Figure 2.9. Percentage of studies on dependency per region based on snowball search carried out in this assessment.

A significant knowledge gap remains in the evidence for dependencies for multiple sectors. Existing studies focus on agriculture, forestry and fishing (about 60 per cent), and about 3 per cent on water supply, sewerage, waste management and remediation, and arts, entertainment and recreation each. There were no studies on, for example, wholesale and retail trade or transportation and storage amongst others. In addition, studies on the agricultural sector mostly analysed pollination effects on crop yield, ignoring other key services such as soil quality, pest control, among others. Most importantly, few studies account for feedback loops in business dependencies that negatively impact biodiversity and reduce its ability to provide benefits. An example is how farming practices affect pollination services and how pollination decline in turn negatively impacts farmers' income. Global, long-term scenarios for biodiversity exist (e.g., Pereira et al., 2010) but are not linked to nature-related business risks (Svartzman et al., 2023).

Several knowledge gaps remain in approaches to understand the dependencies of businesses on nature's contribution to people and the associated magnitude and risk or the trade-offs that exist due to such dependencies. This includes the limited application of diverse methods being used in understanding dependencies and trade-offs, and failing to understand, and account for, the implications for IPLC. Dependences which extend beyond species to their genetic resources such as the use of DSI by businesses for economic gain remain unknown and is key to the implementation of initiatives such as the Cali Fund (Orozco & Scholz, 2025). These gaps, plus the lack of long-term, longitudinal studies, limit understanding of sustainable business reliance on biodiversity. Addressing these issues requires better data collection, cross-disciplinary collaboration, and inclusion of diverse knowledge systems. These knowledge gaps have been populated in **Table 2.11**.

Table 2.11. Knowledge gaps

Context/Section	Knowledge gap
Method (data) (2.3)	Biophysical and ecological approaches are widely used but often lack sufficient data—especially in remote areas and for understudied species—limiting accurate nature’s contributions to people measurement and predictive models.
Method (2.3)	Socio-cultural methods, while valuable, are not used often and hard to standardize and scale for business use and benchmarking.
Typology of dependency (2.2)	Existing tools allow measuring certain nature’s contributions to people in certain locations, but large knowledge gaps and data constraints remain in quantifying spatial and temporally explicit dependencies. This means that methods to better disentangle the contributions of natural, produced, social and human capital to a production process, and such analyses need to become more spatially and temporally detailed.
Method and IPLCs (2.3 and 2.6)	IPLCs knowledge is rarely integrated into formal analyses due to limited ethical and effective mechanisms
Method (integration) (2.3)	Integrated methods like natural capital accounting face challenges in merging diverse data and balancing ecological, economic, and social trade-offs.
Methods and data (2.3)	Available academic methods are only partially reflected in private sector tools, and these tools and associated data are fragmented and sometimes inaccessible.
Business reporting (2.4)	Lack of consistent, self-reported data and information on dependencies and risks by individual businesses.
Business reporting (2.4)	Standardized business-relevant indicators and metrics for assessing nature-related dependencies and risks are absent.
Scenarios (2.4)	Consistent and established scenario data and modelling approaches for nature-related risks, not only for shocks but also for long-term futures, are missing or not applied consistently and comprehensively to identify sustainable business strategies. The IPBES Nature Futures Framework may provide a useful starting point.
Scientific studies on business dependencies (2.4)	<p>Dependencies at the level of individual businesses are studied for only a limited subset of sectors and most of the assessments are related to economic valuation or productivity, there is a significant lack regarding quality and risk of the dependency.</p> <p>Socio-cultural valuation methods tend to focus on understanding the valuation of nature’s contributions to people in order to integrate the value of nature into public sector decision-making. Few studies are conducted in the context of businesses’ dependencies on biodiversity, and if so, the sectors are skewed towards agriculture, forestry, and tourism.</p>

<p>Magnitude of dependency (2.4)</p>	<p>Lack of a comprehensive peer-reviewed database on the dependence of economic sectors on nature's contributions to people. To date, the only such database (ENCORE, n.d.) is not peer-reviewed, highlighting a significant disconnect between market requirements and scientific knowledge.</p> <p>Very few studies evaluate the sustainability of business use of nature's contributions to people that they depend on, because dependency analyses fail to include stock and pressure/trend analyses {2.4}.</p>
<p>Implications of business dependencies on nature for Indigenous Peoples and local communities (2.7)</p>	<p>As few businesses are aware of their dependencies on biodiversity, there is even less awareness within the private sector of how business dependencies on biodiversity affects IPLCs.</p>

2.10. References

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Chapter 2. How does business depend on biodiversity?

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